

ELSA Training Curriculum for Data Scientists

Version 2.0

Maria Christoforaki

30.11.2024

Inhalt

Zusammenfassung	4
1 Introduction	10
2 Feedback on the first version	11
2.1 Survey results	12
2.1.1 Shift-Hub survey	12
2.1.2 Feedback from Industry and Broader Community Surveys	13
2.2 Combined Results and Conclusions	14
3 ELSA Curriculum	17
3.1 Motivation	17
3.2 Need Diagnosis	17
3.3 Curriculum Objectives and Vision	19
3.3 General Topics Outline and Learning Objectives	20
3.4 Selection and Organisation of Content	24
3.4.1 The CRISP-DM Model	24
3.4.2 Mapping Data Science Ethical Considerations to the CRISP-DM model	26
3.4.3 Organization of Content: ELSA Curriculum for Data Scientists Modules	28
Module I: Business understanding	29
KU I.1: Stakeholder identification	29
KU I.2: Incorporating community values	29
KU I.3: Organisational culture	30
KU I.4: Basic Legal Concepts	30
Module II: Data Understanding	30
KU II.1: Data Protection	31
KU II.2: Data bias during collection and ways to mitigate it	31
KU II.3: Intellectual property issues and licences	32
KU II.4: Ethics dumping in data collection	32
KU II.5: Dataset documentation	32
Module III: Data preparation	33
KU III.1: Data Protection	33
KU III.2: Data challenges in preprocessing	33
KU III.3: Intellectual property issues of training data	33
KU III.4: Ethics dumping in data preprocessing	34
KU III.5: Dataset documentation	34
Module IV: Modelling	34
KU IV.1: Model bias and mitigation techniques	34
KU IV.2: Model transparency and explicability	35

KU IV.3: Environmental impact of model training	35
KU IV.4: Intellectual property issues	35
KU IV.5: Model documentation	36
Module V: Evaluation	36
KU V.1: Evaluation beyond accuracy	36
KU V.2: Fairness	36
KU V.3: Model documentation	37
Module VI: Deployment	37
KU VI.1: System deployment limitations	37
KU VI.2: Visualisation bias	38
KU VI.3: Accountability and processes to ensure it	38
3.5 Means of Content Delivery: Selection and Organization of the Learning Experience	39
3.5.1 Implementation Strategies	39
3.5.2 Classroom Techniques	42
Who should teach	42
The Choice of Learning Experiences (LE) and Course Formats	42
3.5.3 Resources for Implementing the Knowledge Units	47
3.6 Evaluation	47
4. The FAIR-DataSpaces Demonstrators as Case Studies	48
4.1 Biodiversity Demonstrator	48
Technical description	48
Application example	50
Ethical and legal concerns exemplified	50
4.2 Data Validation and Quality Assurance	51
Technical description	51
Application example	51
Ethical and legal concerns exemplified	52
4.3 Cross-Platform FAIR Data Analysis	53
Technical description	53
Application example	55
Ethical and legal concerns exemplified	56
5. Conclusions	56
References	57
Appendices	60
Appendix I: KUs Table	61
Appendix II-Survey results	62
A. Horizon Europe Shift-Hub Project Open Innovation Workshop Survey Results	62
B. ELSA Training Survey in English	68
ELSA Training Survey queries	68

Results	70
C. ELSA Training Survey in German	74
ELSA-Ausbildungsumfrage-Fragen	74
Results	77
D. Combined results of the survey in English and German	79
E. Combined results of all surveys	83
E1. Graphs of results	83
E2. Comparative table for each survey and combined results	86

Zusammenfassung

Das Projekt FAIR-Data Spaces konzentriert sich auf den Aufbau von auffindbaren, zugänglichen, interoperablen und wiederverwendbaren cloudbasierten Datenräumen in Zusammenarbeit von Wissenschaft und Wirtschaft, indem es Gaia-X und NFDI zusammenbringt.

Der Aufbau eines solchen Datenraums wäre jedoch unzureichend, wenn sich die Datenwissenschaftler/innen, die ihn aufbauen, nicht über die ethischen, rechtlichen und gesellschaftlichen Aspekte (Ethical Legal and Societal Aspects-ELSA) ihrer Arbeit im Klaren wären. Daher gibt es neben den Anwendungssoftware-Demonstratoren des FAIR-Data Spaces Projekts noch ein weiteres Vorhaben: die Entwicklung eines ELSA-Lehrplans für Datenwissenschaftler/innen im Rahmen des AP 4.5 ELSA Training für Data Scientists. In diesem Bericht stellen wir die zweite und abschließende Version des oben genannten Curriculums vor und zeigen, wie die Software-Demonstratoren, die im Rahmen des Projekts als FAIR-Data Spaces-Demonstratoren entwickelt werden, als Anwendungsfälle für das Unterrichtsprogramm eingesetzt werden können, das auf dem Curriculum basieren wird.

Die erste Version des ELSA-Curriculums wurde im Projektbericht „E4.5.3: ELSA-Trainingscurriculum Version 1“ präsentiert. Bei der Entwicklung der vorliegenden Version haben wir das Feedback aus einer Reihe von Workshops berücksichtigt, die wir organisiert haben, und speziell zu diesem Zweck Umfragen erstellt (siehe „E4.5.4 Workshop-Bericht“ vom 31.3.24), was dazu führte, dass ein modularer Ansatz in die Umsetzungsstrategie des Curriculums aufgenommen wurde. Diese Version aktualisiert auch die Verwendung der FAIR Data Spaces-Demonstratoren als Anwendungsfälle für das ELSA-Curriculum, da sie die Ergebnisse des Arbeitspakets AP2 „*Rechtliche und ethische Rahmenbedingungen*“ bezüglich der rechtlichen und ethischen Überprüfung der Demonstratoren und insbesondere des Projektberichts „E2.2.1: Bericht Vertragsrechtliche Überprüfung und Compliance“ (Breß et al. 2023) berücksichtigt. Es gibt auch minimale Änderungen in der Struktur und der Formulierung des Berichts sowie in den Anhängen

Der Bericht ist in die folgenden Sektionen unterteilt: detaillierte Präsentation des Feedbacks, das wir über Workshops und Umfragen erhalten haben; die Beschreibung des Curriculums mit Sub-Sektionen über die Motivation, Bedarfsanalyse, Auswahl und Organisation des Materials, Mittel zur Bereitstellung der Inhalte und Evaluierungsvorschläge; die Präsentation der FAIR-Data Spaces-Demonstratoren als Anwendungsfälle für das Curriculum; Schlussfolgerungen, gefolgt von den Anhängen.

Um die erste Version des Curriculums zu bewerten, sind wir auf zwei Wegen vorgegangen:

1. Wir haben eine Reihe von Workshops durchgeführt. Die Ergebnisse wurden im „E4.5.4 Workshop-Bericht“ vom 31.3.24 veröffentlicht.
2. Wir haben drei Umfragen zum Inhalt des Curriculums und zur vorgeschlagenen Form der Umsetzung durchgeführt.

Die abschließenden Überlegungen aus dem erhaltenen Feedback lassen sich wie folgt zusammenfassen:

- 1) Inhalt:
 - a) Rechtliche Fragen: Rechtliche Grundbegriffe, Datenschutz, Transparenz und Immaterialgüterrechte werden als am wichtigsten für die Schulung erachtet.
 - b) Ethische Fragen wie Voreingenommenheit oder Umweltauswirkungen stehen weiter unten auf der Liste, und die berufsethischen Grundsätze stehen ebenfalls weiter unten.
- 2) Dauer des Trainings: Es besteht eine klare Bevorzugung für kurze und fokussierte Trainings. Workshops gelten als die am besten geeignete Trainingsform.
- 3) Niveau des Wissens:
 - a) Sowohl Einführungs- als auch Spezialprogramme sind erforderlich, je nach Zielgruppe, Dauer und Form.
 - b) Das Training sollte sich an alle richten, die in irgendeiner Weise an einem datenwissenschaftlichen Projekt beteiligt sind, seien es Datenwissenschaftler/innen (Anfänger und Experten) oder Manager.
- 4) Trainingsanbieter: Akademische Institutionen wurden als geeigneter für die Durchführung eines solchen Kurses erachtet (im Vergleich zu privaten Unternehmen oder Institutionen, entweder im Rahmen ihres Studienangebots oder als eigenständige Programme).

Um die Bedarfsanalyse für ein ELSA-Curriculum für Datenwissenschaftler/innen zu erstellen, führten wir eine Landschaftsbeschreibung auf der Grundlage einer Literaturrecherche, einer Reihe von Community-Workshops und nach der Präsentation der ersten Curriculum-Version eine Reihe von Umfragen durch.

Die wichtigsten Erkenntnisse aus der Bedarfsdiagnose waren:

- Das universitäre Angebot an ELSA-Kursen ist derzeit nicht ausreichend
- Datenwissenschaftler/innen sind der Meinung, dass die sozialen Auswirkungen von Verzerrungen in Daten und Modellen und die Beeinträchtigung der Privatsphäre des Einzelnen die größten Probleme der Datenwissenschaft sind.
- Was das Profil der Datenwissenschaftler/innen angeht, so sind die meisten von ihnen männlich, relativ jung und haben einen akademischen Abschluss. Es gibt jedoch auch eine beträchtliche Anzahl von Personen, die keinen Abschluss haben.
- Je nach Rolle und Beteiligung eines/einer Datenwissenschaftlers/in in der Datenwissenschaft/Maschinelles Lernen-Pipeline gibt es unterschiedliche

Bildungsbedürfnisse in Bezug auf die Art der zu behandelnden Themen sowie die Form der Umsetzung des Programms.

Aufgrund dieser Erkenntnisse wurden die Zielfächer für den Lehrplan festgelegt und seine Vision und Lernziele bestimmt, nämlich dass Datenwissenschaftler/innen in der Lage sein sollten:

1. Ethische, rechtliche und gesellschaftliche Aspekte ihrer Arbeit zu erkennen (Awareness).
2. Eine gemeinsame Sprache mit den zuständigen Fachleuten zu sprechen, um gemeinsam nach geeigneten Lösungen zu suchen (Kommunikationsfähigkeit).
3. ELSA in den Data-Science-Workflow einzubinden und nicht als Hindernis oder überflüssiges Artefakt zu betrachten, sondern als integralen Bestandteil des Data-Science-Projektlebenszyklus (Aufbau einer professionellen Mentalität).

Der letzte Punkt führte zur Verwendung des CRISP-DM-Modells als Grundlage für den Aufbau des Lehrplans. CRoss - Industry Standard Process for Data Mining - ist ein nicht-proprietäres, frei verfügbares Data-Mining-Modell, das unabhängig von einem bestimmten Tool oder einer bestimmten Anwendung ist. Sein Ziel ist es, Best Practices zu fördern und Organisationen die Struktur zu bieten, die sie für die Umsetzung von Data-Mining-Projekten benötigen. CRISP-DM gliedert den Data-Mining-Prozess in sechs Phasen: Geschäftsverständnis, Datenverständnis, Datenaufbereitung, Modellierung, Bewertung und Einsatz (business understanding, data understanding, data preparation, modelling, evaluation, and deployment) (Shearer 2000)

Die Gründe, die für diese Wahl sprechen, können wie folgt genannt werden:

1. Es ist bekannt und wird häufig in Data-Science-Projekten verwendet.
2. Es wurde bereits verwendet, um ethische und rechtliche Fragen zu den verschiedenen Phasen des Modells darzustellen und Rahmenwerke zu entwickeln, die die Anwendung ethischer Standards bei der Entwicklung von Data-Science-Projekten gewährleisten.
3. Für ein Projekt wie FAIR Data Spaces, das auf die Zusammenarbeit zwischen Forschung und Industrie abzielt, ist die Tatsache, dass es hauptsächlich von der Industrie entwickelt wurde, ebenfalls relevant

Die Struktur des Curriculums hat eine vertikale und eine horizontale Unterteilung. Die vertikale Gliederung besteht aus Modulen, die den CRISP-DM-Phasen entsprechen, während die horizontale Gliederung aus Wissensteilen besteht, die zu drei phasenübergreifenden Bereichen gehören, nämlich ethische und gesellschaftliche, rechtliche und technische Wissensteilen (Knowledge Units-KUs).

Ethische und gesellschaftliche Wissensteile:

Ethische und gesellschaftliche Aspekte der Datenwissenschaft reichen von der Identifizierung der Stakeholder als jede Gruppe oder Einzelperson, die sich auf das Erreichen der Lernziele

auswirkt oder davon betroffen ist, über die Einbeziehung von Gemeinschaftswerten in die eigene Arbeit, die Vermeidung von Diskriminierung von Einzelpersonen oder Gruppen (insbesondere von gefährdeten Gruppen), ethisches Dumping, die Berücksichtigung der Umweltauswirkungen der datenwissenschaftlichen Anwendungen bis hin zur Übernahme von Verantwortung und Rechenschaftspflicht für die eigenen Entscheidungen und Handlungen.

Rechtliche WissensBausteine:

Das Lernziel dieser Einheiten ist es, Datenwissenschaftler/innen bei der Bewältigung rechtlicher Probleme zu unterstützen, mit denen sie bei ihrer Arbeit konfrontiert werden könnten. Wir zielen nicht darauf ab, sie in die Lage zu versetzen, diese Probleme selbst zu lösen, eine Aufgabe, die bereits hochspezialisiertes Wissen von Domänenexperten/innen erfordert.

Das Lernziel in Bezug auf Datenwissenschaftler ist ein dreifaches:

1. Sie für die rechtlichen Fragen zu sensibilisieren, mit denen sie im Laufe ihrer Arbeit höchstwahrscheinlich konfrontiert werden.
2. Ihnen einen Überblick über die grundlegenden rechtlichen Konzepte zu geben, die sie zum Verständnis der oben genannten Fragen benötigen.
3. Ihnen das Vokabular an die Hand zu geben, das sie benötigen, um effektiv mit den Fachleuten (z.B. Rechtswissenschaftlern/innen) zu kommunizieren, mit denen sie bei der Lösung dieser Probleme zusammenarbeiten müssen.

Technische WissensEinheiten:

Diese Einheiten befassen sich mit der technischen Umsetzung rechtlicher oder ethischer Wünsche wie dem Datenschutz, der Erkennung von Verzerrungen durch Daten und Algorithmen und Strategien zur Milderung dieser Verzerrungen, der Integration von Fairness, Effektivität und Erklärbarkeit in die Bewertung eines datenwissenschaftlichen Projekts, der Bereitstellung und Überwachung außerhalb von Experimentier- und Testumgebungen. Das Curriculum wird keine spezifische technische Schulung zu diesen Themen anbieten, sondern vielmehr anhand von Anwendungsfällen veranschaulichen, wie technische Lösungen eingesetzt werden können.

Die Gründe dafür sind unter anderem die Tatsache, dass jeder Anwendungsbereich spezifische Techniken erfordert und dass Themen wie Sicherheit, Datenverschlüsselung, Datenintegrität, Authentifizierung, gegnerische Angriffe usw. in der Regel in speziellen Kursen während des Studiums oder in der Praxis der Datenwissenschaft behandelt werden.

Die Umsetzungsstrategie, die zur Anwendung des Curriculums verfolgt wird, hängt von den zur Verfügung stehenden Ressourcen und der Zeit sowie von der Zielgruppe ab. Auch der Anwendungsbereich ist ein wichtiger Faktor: Die Umsetzung eines datenwissenschaftlichen

Projekts für das Marketing stellt andere Herausforderungen als eines im Healthcare-Bereich. In seiner Konzeption versucht das Curriculum, ein allgemeines Publikum mit geringen Kenntnissen über ELSA-Themen in datenwissenschaftlichen Projekten anzusprechen. Wir sind uns jedoch bewusst, dass dies selten der Fall ist. Wir schlagen die folgenden Umsetzungsstrategien vor:

- Einführungskurs unter der Annahme, dass nur wenig oder gar kein Wissen über ELSA vorhanden ist.
- Auswahl von Modulen, die zu den Rollen der Zielgruppe passen.
- Anpassung des Inhalts an den Anwendungsbereich, der die Zielgruppe interessiert.
- Eine Kombination der beiden vorherigen Strategien.

Daher unterscheiden wir zwischen vier Arten von Modulen:

1. **Kernmodule:** Diese Module vermitteln Grundwissen zu ELSA-Themen im Bereich der Datenwissenschaft.
2. **Rollenspezifische Module:** Je nach Rolle, die ein/e Datenwissenschaftler/in in einem Projekt innehat, kann er/sie sich für eine Vertiefung in bestimmte Wissensbereiche entscheiden, wie z. B. Datenschutz, Identifizierung von Stakeholdern oder Herausforderungen bei der Datenaufbereitung.
3. **Domänenspezifische Module:** Diese Module richten sich an Fachleute aus bestimmten Anwendungsbereichen, z. B. Healthcare, NLP oder Bildverarbeitung. Ihr Inhalt könnte die Anpassung der allgemeinen Module an die Herausforderungen der spezifischen Anwendung oder des technischen Bereichs sein.
4. **Eine Kombination der beiden vorherigen Arten von Modulen** wäre ebenfalls möglich, z. B. ein halbtägiger Workshop über Datenschutzfragen für Projectmanagers oder ein zweitägiger Workshop über die Identifizierung und Minderung von Daten- und Model-Bias für technische Leitung und/oder Entwickler bei der Entwicklung von Chatbots im Healthcare.

Was die Unterrichtstechniken betrifft, so können diese von Vorlesungen, eingeladenen Vorträgen und Case Studies bis hin zu kooperativen Lerntechniken wie Studentearbeitsgruppen und Rollenspielen oder praktischen Übungen reichen. Unsere Literaturrecherche hat jedoch ergeben, dass die effektivsten Mittel zur Vermittlung von Inhalten praktische Übungen und die Verwendung von Fallstudien sind.

Wir stellen die Vor- und Nachteile jeder Art von Lernerfahrung auf Basis der relevanten Bibliografie vor. Die Lehrkräfte jeder KU entscheiden, welches Material bei der Umsetzung des Lehrplans verwendet wird. Es kann je nach gewählter Umsetzungsstrategie angepasst werden.

Die Teilnehmenden können anhand ihres Engagements in den verschiedenen Modulen bewertet werden, während die Programmbewertung durch Rückmeldungen sowohl der Teilnehmenden

als auch der Ausbilder darüber erfolgen kann, ob das Programm ihre Erwartungen erfüllt hat oder nicht. In diesem Sinne ist der beste Weg zur Evaluierung des Curriculums die Durchführung eines Pilotunterrichtsprogramms, gefolgt von einer detaillierten Evaluierung anhand von Bewertungsbögen der Teilnehmenden und TutorInnen oder von Interviews. Dies liegt jedoch nicht im Rahmen des FAIR Data Spaces Projekts.

Die FAIR-Data Spaces Demonstratoren als Use Cases für das Curriculum

Im Rahmen des FAIR Data Spaces Projekts werden drei Demonstratoren entwickelt: a. für einen Datenraum für Biodiversität, b. Qualitätssicherung von Forschungsdaten und c. plattformübergreifende Datenanalyse. Diese drei Demonstratoren werden als Use Cases für das ELSA Curriculum vorgeschlagen. Zu diesem Zweck haben wir Beiträge aus dem AP2-Arbeitspaket "Rechtliche und ethische Rahmenbedingungen" zur rechtlichen und ethischen Überprüfung der Demonstratoren verwendet.

In Sektion 4 finden Sie eine kurze technische Beschreibung jedes Demonstrators mit einem Anwendungsszenario und den ethischen und rechtlichen Fragen, die in jedem dieser Demonstratoren zum Ausdruck kommen. Dazu gehören: der Schutz persönlicher Daten, der Schutz des Urheberrechts und des geistigen Eigentums, Fragen der Voreingenommenheit und der Diskriminierung sowie Fragen, die sich aus dem Datenaustausch zwischen Industrie und Wissenschaft ergeben, ein Thema, das für das FAIR Data Spaces Projekt von besonderer Bedeutung ist.

Die zweite und finale Version des ELSA-Curriculums für Data Scientist wird als Bericht vorgelegt, nachdem wir das Feedback unserer Gaia-X-Industriepartner (und der gesamten Community) zur Nachhaltigkeit des Curriculums eingeholt haben. In dieser Version wird der Einsatz der FAIR Data Spaces-Demonstratoren als Anwendungsfälle aktualisiert werden, da mehr Input von den AP2-Projektteilnehmern in Form von Projektleistungen zur Verfügung gestellt wird.

1 Introduction

The FAIR-Data Spaces project focuses on building findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable cloud-based Data Spaces with the cooperation of science and business by bringing together two initiatives, namely Gaia-X and NFDI.

The construction of such a data space could not be adequate if the data scientists who are actually building it are not aware of the Ethical, Legal, and Social Aspects (ELSA) of their work.

Thus, in addition to the FAIR-Data Spaces project application software demonstrators, there is also another one, namely the development of an ELSA Curriculum for data scientists.

In this report, we present the second and final version of an ELSA Curriculum for data scientists and explain how the software applications developed as FAIR-Data Spaces demonstrators within the project can be deployed as use cases for the instruction program based on the Curriculum.

The first version of the ELSA Curriculum was presented in the deliverable “E4.5.3: ELSA-Trainingscurriculum Version 1”, also published in the FAIR Data Spaces Zenodo community (Christoforaki 2023), which with the “E4.5.1: Bewertung der bestehenden Ansätze” deliverable formed the basis for a journal publication (Christoforaki and Beyan 2024). In the development of the present version, we took into account the feedback that was given via a number of Workshops we organised and surveys created explicitly for this purpose (reported in “E4.5.4 Workshop-Bericht” of 31.3.24), resulting in adding a modular approach in the Curriculum implementation strategy. This version also updates the use of the FAIR Data Spaces demonstrators as use cases for the ELSA Curriculum since it takes into consideration the output of AP2 *Rechtliche und ethische Rahmenbedingungen* work package regarding the Legal and Ethical Review of the Demonstrators and specifically from “E2.2.1: Bericht Vertragsrechtliche Überprüfung und Compliance” project deliverable (Breß et al. 2023). There are also minor changes in the structure and the phrasing of the report, as well as the appendices. Overall, we aim to present a more robust approach based on both the feedback mentioned and the augmentation of the bibliographical resources used.

The rest of the report is structured as follows: in [Section 2](#), there is a detailed presentation of the feedback we received via Workshops and Surveys; in [Section 3](#) we present the curriculum itself, including the motivation, needs diagnosis, selection and organisation of the material, means of content delivery and evaluation suggestions; in [Section 4](#), we describe the FAIR-Data Spaces as Use Cases for the curriculum: first we offer a technical description for each demonstrator and then the ELSA issues that can be underlined in each case; [Section 5](#) closes the report with conclusions followed by the [Appendices](#).

2 Feedback on the first version

In order to assess the first curriculum version, we followed two ways:

- a. We conducted a series of workshops. The results have been reported in “E4.5.4 Workshop-Bericht” of 31.3.24.
- b. We gave out three surveys with similar questions regarding the Curriculum content and the proposed form of implementation.

We summarise the survey results in the following section. Detailed reports for each survey are in [Appendix II](#).

2.1 Survey results

2.1.1 Shift-Hub survey

The first one took place on 13.6.23 in the Horizon Europe Shift-Hub Open Innovation Project framework. Shift-Hub¹ is a Horizon Europe project that aims to establish a pan-European Smart Innovation Hub paving the way towards the future federated European Health Data Space. The University Hospital of Cologne is a project partner in ShiftHub via the Institute of Biomedical Informatics. In this framework, an Open Innovation Workshop took place on July 13, 2023, where we had the opportunity to receive input from the participants regarding five ELSA-related/relevant questions using sli.do² to collect answers. The results were reported in “E4.5.4 Workshop-Bericht” of 31.3.24. We repeat the results here for the sake of completeness and because we will combine them with the results from the other two surveys to compile our conclusions.

The survey contained questions about the subjects, the format, the knowledge level, the type of trainees, and the kind of organisation that would be most suitable to provide this kind of training. For each question, the most common answers were:

- Subjects: The most popular subject was *Stakeholder identification and impact assessment* (75%). This is understandable, given that the partners of Shift-Hub are organisations and academic institutions that want to create a Health Data Hub, a Smart Health Apps Repository and an online Marketplace. The following most popular subjects were *Basic legal concepts* (40%) and *Intellectual Property* (36%) as well as *Evaluation beyond accuracy* (36%), which was also to be expected, taking into consideration the nature of the Workshop participants.
- Regarding the format of the training, the most popular option was a *Workshop on specific topics (2-3 days per topic)* (48%), followed by *Summer or Winter School (1-2 Weeks)* (24%)
- Regarding the level of knowledge that training should offer, the participants replied that there should be both introductory and deep dives into specific topics (e.g., legal issues) depending on the audience (40%), the second choice being only Deep dives (32%), probably because the participants judged that most people already have some ELSA knowledge, and what they need is more in-depth teaching.
- Related to the previous question, when asked what kind of audience is appropriate for this training, they overwhelmingly (64%) answered that both experienced practitioners and novices, as well as managers and technical directors, are suitable audiences, depending on the format and duration.

¹ <https://shift-hub.eu/>

² <https://www.slido.com/>

- Finally, regarding who should provide the course, the participants' first choice was specialised training centres (44%) and, as a second option, academic institutions in the form of independent programmes addressed to all interested parties (40%).

The detailed results can be found in Appendix II [A. Horizon Europe Shift-Hub Project Open Innovation Workshop Survey Results](#)

2.1.2 Feedback from Industry and Broader Community Surveys

In fulfilment of WP4.5.4: *Outreach and contacting Gaia-X partners*, we consulted with the Gaia-X hub in Germany to discuss how we could most efficiently collect feedback on the ELSA curriculum from their members. They advised us to conduct a survey, so we created one, which they then distributed to their members. The survey ran until the end of March 2024, and in collaboration with AP1 *Roadmapping and Community*, we have extended its target audience to the general community via the FAIR Data Spaces newsletter. The survey is available in English and German to maximise participation.

The survey queries and results can be found in Appendix II [B. ELSA Training Survey In English](#) and [C. ELSA Training Survey In German](#) for each language respectively.

According to their own declarations, most participants were computer/data scientists or engineers working in biomedical/health informatics and digital humanities.

Here, we summarise the results for both the English and German language surveys since they were conducted simultaneously and addressed to the same audience. The combined results for both versions can be found in Appendix III [D. Combined results of the survey in English and German](#). Specifically:

- Subjects: The most popular subject was *Data protection* (19%), followed by *Basic legal concepts* (17%) and *Transparency and explicability* (16%).
- Regarding the format of the training, the most popular option was *Summer or Winter School (1-2 Weeks)* (33%) followed by *Workshops on special topics (4 half days per topic)* (29%) and *Workshop on specific topics (2-3 days per topic)* (26%).
- Regarding the level of knowledge that training should offer, the participants replied that there should be both introductory and deep dives into specific topics (e.g. legal issues) depending on the audience (50%), while 31% said it depended on the duration.
- When asked what kind of audience is appropriate for this training, just like in the Shift-Hub survey, they overwhelmingly (65%) answered that both experienced practitioners and novices, as well as managers and technical directors, are suitable audiences, depending on the format and duration.

- Finally, on the question of who should provide the course, the participants' first choice was *Academic Institutions as independent programs addressed to all that are interested* (40%), followed by *Academic Institutions as part of their studies* (31%).

2.2 Combined Results and Conclusions

When we combine the results of all surveys, we get the following picture (detailed graphs can be found in Appendix II [E. Combined results of all surveys](#)):

- Subjects: The most popular subject is still *Data protection* (14%), followed by *Basic legal concepts* (15%), while *Transparency and explicability* (13%) is equally important with *Stakeholder identification* (13%).
- Format of training: the preferred format was *Workshop on specific topics (2-3 days per topic)* with (35%) (followed by *Workshop on specific topics (2-3 days per topic)* with (35%).
- Regarding the level of knowledge the training should offer, the participants replied that there should be both introductory and deep dives into specific topics (e.g. legal issues) depending on the audience (46%). In comparison, 28% said it depended on the duration.
- When asked what kind of audience is appropriate for this training, 64% answered that both experienced practitioners and novices, as well as managers and technical directors, are suitable audiences, depending on the format and duration.
- Finally, on the question of who should provide the course, the participants' first choice was *Academic Institutions as independent programs addressed to all that are interested* (41%), followed by *Specialised training centres* (27%) and *Academic Institutions as part of their studies* (31%).

[Table 1](#) shows the subjects prioritised in each survey in comparison (for a detailed comparative table regarding all questions, see Appendix II [E2.Comparative table for each survey and combined results](#)). We observe noticeable differences between the Shift-Hub and the Internet surveys (English and German). For example, if we rank the proposed subjects that the ELSA Curriculum should address, then we get the following results :

Internet survey	Shift-Hub	Total
Data protection	Stakeholder identification and impact assessment	Basic legal concepts
Basic legal concepts	Basic legal concepts	Data protection
Transparency and explicability	Intellectual Property	Stakeholder identification and impact assessment

Bias and mitigation	Evaluation beyond accuracy	Transparency and explicability
Intellectual Property	Transparency and explicability	Intellectual Property
Professional codes of values/conduct	Environmental impact of model training	Bias and mitigation
Environmental impact of model training	Data protection	Evaluation beyond accuracy
Stakeholder identification and impact assessment	Professional codes of values/conduct	Environmental impact of model training
Evaluation beyond accuracy	Bias and mitigation	Professional codes of values/conduct
Auditing	Auditing	Auditing

Table 1 Survey comparative results.

We can make similar observations regarding the rest of the questions. We can attribute the discrepancy to the following factors:

1. The people who participated in the surveys belong to different communities. The Shift-Hub project aims to develop a community regarding the use of smart health apps. They are senior researchers, work for companies or are representatives of civil society. Therefore, it is natural that they see stakeholder identification as the most important topic compared to the other topics on the list. On the other hand, the Internet survey was addressed to the whole community, and the people who took part self-identified as mostly IT-related.
2. The Shift-Hub survey took place during a workshop, where the ELSA Curriculum was presented before answering the survey. On the other hand, the internet survey, although it had a reference to the related documents (the ELSA Curriculum deliverable and the FAIR-Data Spaces webpage), there is no way to know whether the people who answered the questions actually informed themselves of the framework or just answered based on their own knowledge and needs.

Regarding the issues the surveys dealt with, we can make the following remarks:

1. Legal issues (basic legal concepts, data protection, transparency, and intellectual property are higher on the list than bias or even auditing (which might also be considered to have legal aspects). Ethical issues like bias or environmental impacts are put in lower places on the list, while the professional codes of ethics are also in a low position. This last observation is supported by the bibliography: (McNamara, Smith, and Murphy-Hill 2018) found that “explicitly instructing [software engineers] to consider the

ACM code of ethics in their decision making had no observed effect when compared with a control group.” According to the authors of the study mentioned above, this poses the question of what other means of teaching ethics would work if professional codes do not. Additionally, (Mittelstadt 2019) suggests a principled approach may have a limited impact on the design and governance of AI due to (among other factors) the fact that AI development lacks proven methods to translate principles into practice.

2. Regarding the duration of the training, there is a clear preference for short and focused training. Workshops are deemed to be the most appropriate form of instruction.
3. Regarding the level of knowledge, both introductory and specialised programmes are required, depending on the audience, the duration, and the form. Flexibility is clearly needed in the way the Curriculum is implemented, and this point will be addressed in this report: we [propose a modular form for the implementation](#) of the curriculum that can be easily adapted to satisfy this demand.
4. The training should be addressed to all who are somehow implicated in a data science project, be they data scientists (novice or expert) or managers. This is another issue that can be easily tackled due to the modular form of the curriculum.
5. As for the training providers, it is also clear that most respondents regarded the academic institutions as more appropriate to implement such a course, either in the context of their study offerings or as independent programmes addressed to anybody interested. There is also strong support for specialised training centres, but not for companies to organise such programmes for their employees. The reason for these preferences may be that the respondents think that academic institutions are more appropriate to organise such a training program since education is their speciality, and they know how to organise and implement educational programmes. Academic institutions also have the personnel and the infrastructure (spaces and equipment), and the same holds for the specialised training centres. On the other hand, companies have different objectives, so an educational program implemented via their HR department would probably not be as effective from a cost and resource perspective. However, a company would be more effective if a focused programme addressed specific issues that better reflected their interests.

In compiling the second version of the ELSA Curriculum, we considered the above remarks and the feedback we received during the Workshops we organised (see “E4.5.4 Workshop-Bericht” of 31.3.24). We updated the content selection and offered examples of how the implementation can be adjusted to the specific audience needs.

3 ELSA Curriculum

3.1 Motivation

The term “data science” appeared in 1974 but took almost 30 years to be identified as a discipline of its own (Emmert-Streib and Dehmer 2019), specifically as an enlargement of “the major areas of technical work of the field of statistics” (Cleveland 2001)

However, the proliferation of data-driven applications (especially with the use of AI in recent years) has brought into the limelight the ethical, legal, and societal aspects (ELSA) of data science - for a comprehensive presentation, see (Crawford 2021).

Some of the ELSA challenges have been the subject of regulation, such as the European Union General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)(European Parliament, Council of the European Union 2016) for the protection of personal data and, more recently, the AI Act (European Commission, Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology 2021), while ethical and societal aspects, have been the subject of recommendations and guidelines by professional, national, international, and supranational organisations and institutions (Christoforaki and Beyan 2022) (Christoforaki and Beyan 2022).

The raising of awareness via ELSA education for AI practitioners is underlined in the European Commission’s high-level expert group on artificial intelligence in their ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI (High-Level Expert Group on AI (AI HLEG) 2019) in order to promote an ethical mindset for all stakeholders, including developers (pp. 23–24), as well as a means to develop accountability practices (p. 31).

The proposal for an ELSA curriculum for data scientists, as presented in this document, is developed in this framework. The next section presents the need diagnosis for such a curriculum.

3.2 Need Diagnosis

To form the need diagnosis for an ELSA Curriculum for data scientists, we followed the paths below:

1. In the context of the FAIRData Spaces project, we have conducted a review of the existing landscape as described in the project deliverable “E4.5.1: Bewertung der bestehenden Ansätze”, also published as a report in the FAIR-DS Zenodo Community (Christoforaki 2021). There, we reviewed the existing data science ethics courses in tertiary education and identified three major topic categories: computer science, professional and business skills, and ethical and legal topics.

2. Additionally, in the Workshop Series reported in the project deliverable “E4.5.2: Workshop-Bericht”, we broadly sketched the profile of the data scientist based on the ideal one as described in the bibliography and the realistic one as painted by surveys (Christoforaki 2022).
3. After the presentation of the first ELSA Curriculum version, we conducted online and in-person surveys where we received feedback on our first suggestions as well as more information regarding the educational needs. The results of these surveys are presented in this report in [2.1 Survey results](#).

The main takeaways from all the above concerning the need diagnosis were:

- Data scientists:
 - Come from computer science and statistics disciplines;
 - A growing number of them also come from other disciplines such as social sciences, finance, and business, a trend that is manifested by the influx of people transitioning from other disciplines to data science, as documented in the [World Economic Forum of 2020 Future of Jobs report](#);
 - However, a considerable number have no degree (since having a degree is not a prerequisite for getting started in data science) and have landed in data science following non- or quasi-academic ways(e.g., online courses).
- Those with an academic education did not necessarily have any ELSA-related courses, either mandatory or elective. The review of university study offers in the US, Europe, and all over the world revealed that few tertiary education institutes offer these kinds of courses (the numbers vary between 15% and 34%, depending on the survey).
- The industry desires but does not require ELSA knowledge for data science employees.
- A growing number of data scientists recognise the need for awareness and action regarding the ELSA challenges in their work. When the data science professionals were asked to point out the biggest problem in data science/machine learning, the respondents identified first the social impacts caused by bias in data and models, followed by impacts on individual privacy.
- Depending on the role and the involvement of a data scientist in the data science/machine learning pipeline, there are different educational needs with respect to both the kinds of topics that should be addressed as well as the form of the implementation of the final program.

As a result, regarding the profile of the data scientist, we have to take into consideration that :

1. There are two kinds of data scientists: one with experience and/or background studies in maths, statistics and visualisation techniques, and a second one with computer science and programming skills acquired either by working experience or computer science/engineering studies.

2. However, a more holistic approach may include people with a social science research background, who are knowledgeable in methods and possess skills used in raising the appropriate questions and hypotheses, as well as those with soft skills associated with communication and teamwork or who have some domain knowledge and business and strategy competencies.
3. In the future, data scientists will not form a homogeneous group, such as university graduates, which is the target group of today's ethics curricula. They will also come from various educational, social, and national backgrounds, and quite a lot of them will land in data science following quasi-academic routes, especially when employed in job positions with less demanding high-end knowledge or education.

These points guide the curriculum's target subjects, which will have to face challenges arising from different educational needs.

3.3 Curriculum Objectives and Vision

Based on our background review to identify the needs an ELSA curriculum for data scientists would address, we composed the proposal presented in this report. Our main concerns were the following:

- Data science projects are multidisciplinary in the following ways:
 - the application domain, for example, just examining scholar publications, at least 20 disciplines can be identified (Emmert-Streib and Dehmer 2019),
 - the implementation of the project requires the cooperation of a variety of experts from many disciplines (computer scientists and engineers, statisticians, visualisation experts, etc.) and
 - the impact of these projects makes cooperation with other stakeholders, such as legal experts, ethicists, and community representatives (such as patients in healthcare projects), necessary.
- ELSA challenges are faced throughout the data science workflow. Some of them run through more than one phase, others not; some may concern all the people involved in the project, others not so much or not to the same degree. In both cases, they have to be considered part of the workflow and not as a sometimes optional task.

The above led us to form the primary objectives of the ELSA Curriculum as follows:

Data scientists should be able to:

1. Recognise Ethical, Legal and Societal Aspects pertaining to their work (Awareness).
2. Possess a common language with the relevant domain experts in order to cooperate to find appropriate solutions (Communication ability).

3. Incorporate ELSA in the data science workflow and not be seen as an impediment or a superfluous artefact rather than an integral part of the Data Science Project Lifecycle (Professional mentality building).

The above objectives can be refined into specific competencies, presented in the next section, which outlines the general topics and defines the Learning outcomes of each topic.

3.3 General Topics Outline and Learning Objectives

In order to achieve the above, data scientists should learn and be able to understand basic concepts belonging to other disciplines (law, ethics, and social sciences), as well as be aware of how the ELSA issues could be practically tackled via the use of specific frameworks, standards and techniques. Specifically, we propose three main area topics:

Ethical and Societal Knowledge Units: Ethical and Social aspects of data science include incorporating community values into one's work, avoiding discrimination against individuals or groups (especially vulnerable ones), considering the environmental impact of the data science applications, and assuming responsibility and accountability for one's decisions and actions.

Business ethics, namely Professional ethics codes and codes of conduct, responsibility and accountability, and leadership.

We devise the content within the framework of the four + 1 ethical principles introduced by (Floridi et al. 2018)³: the four bioethics principles, namely, Autonomy, Non-maleficence, Beneficence and Justice, and Transparency and their manifestation in data science projects.

The bioethics principles, as presented in (Beauchamp and Childress 2019), are rephrased and augmented by transparency in (Floridi et al. 2018) as follows:

- **Autonomy:** in bioethics, is connected to liberty as independence from controlling influences and agency as the capacity for intentional action so that an individual can act freely according to their own plan. Regarding Data Science applications, the focus is on the balance between decision-making automation (what kind of decision can and should be made by artificial agents or humans).
- **Nonmaleficence:** in bioethics, nonmaleficence is the principle of not inflicting, preventing, or removing harm, while in data science, it can be seen as the prevention of accidental or deliberate harm.

³ (Floridi et al. 2018) present the principles regarding AI. Although data science and AI are not synonymous, we regard them as facing similar issues with respect to ELSA. We will use the term Data Science in accordance with the project terminology.

- **Beneficence:** requires that we refrain from harming people and contribute to their welfare. In the context of Data Science applications, this might also include promoting their well-being, preserving their dignity, and sustaining the planet.
- **Justice:** can be interpreted in bioethics as fair, equitable, and appropriate treatment. Analogously, Data Science applications should promote prosperity and preserve solidarity by trying to correct past wrongs, such as eliminating unfair discrimination, ensuring that the created benefits are shared or at least shareable and preventing the creation of new harms, such as the undermining of existing social structures.
- **Transparency:** via explicability, can ensure that the decision-making process can be understood and held accountable.

The original Bioethics principles and their Data Science counterparts are presented in [Table 2](#)

Principle	Bioethics(Beauchamp and Childress 2019)	DS/AI (Floridi et al. 2018)
Autonomy	act freely in accordance with a self-chosen plan liberty agency	contain the risk of delegating too much to machines humans should always retain the power to decide which decisions to take
Non-maleficence	not inflict evil or harm prevent evil or harm remove evil or harm	prevent harms arising, whether from the intent of humans or the unpredicted behaviour of machines
Beneficence	actively promote good	promote well-being preserve dignity sustain the planet
Justice	fair, equitable, and appropriate treatment	Prevent/eliminate discrimination equally shared benefits
Explicability		understand and hold accountable the decision-making processes of AI

Table 2. The principles of Bioethics and their AI renditions

Legal Knowledge Units: The objective of these units is to help data scientists cope with legal issues they might be facing in their course of work. The objective is not to make them able to solve these problems, which demands highly specialised knowledge and should be left to specifically trained domain experts, but to :

- a. Make them aware of the legal issues they will most probably face during the course of their work
- b. Give them an overview of the basic legal concepts they need to understand the issues mentioned above, and
- c. provide them with the vocabulary that they need in order to communicate effectively with the domain experts (such as legal scholars) who will be the ones that will provide the solution in each specific situation.

The main areas that will be covered are data protection (especially as demanded by GDPR), intellectual property issues related to data science (e.g., training data), and basic legal terminology and concepts.

Technical Renderings Knowledge Units: While technical solutions can be employed to comply with a wide variety of ethical or legal demands, these units do not aim to teach technical skills to data scientists. These skills may be covered in other specific courses during their studies or practice and concern broader domains, such as security issues like encryption, data integrity, authentication, adversarial attacks, etc.

They will rather deal with technical renderings of legal or ethical desiderata like privacy, data and algorithmic bias detection and mitigation strategies, incorporation of fairness, effectiveness and explainability in the evaluation of a data science project, deployment and monitoring outside experimental/testing environments. The Curriculum will not provide specific technical training regarding these issues since each application domain might require specific techniques; rather, it will illustrate how technical solutions can be employed via use cases.

[Table 3](#) defines the expected learning outcomes for each topic:

Topic	Learning Outcome
Basic Legal concepts	-know the various kinds of law (e.g. cyberlaw) -understand the national vs international and EU law and how these relate -understand concepts like accountability, liability and compliance
Data Protection Law	-understand the basic concepts as defined in Data Protection Law (GDPR): personal and sensitive data, data subject and their rights, data controller and data processor, the role of the DPO and legal grounds for processing of personal data, Data minimisation, Availability, Integrity, Confidentiality, Unlinkability, Transparency and Intervenability and

Topic	Learning Outcome
	international data transfer
Intellectual Property	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -understand basic concepts: --licences that data come with, the permissible ways for data collection using copyrighted works as training datasets, legally storing them for the training process, copyright on the generated data --IP issues regarding the code used (models) and produced
Business aspects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Identify the stakeholders -incorporate professional norms and principles -identify the impact of the organisational culture of the corporation they work for by assessing their procedures and practices for guiding and supporting ethical behaviour -explain the system limitations to the clients
Bias, discrimination and fairness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -understand what bias is -identify different kinds of fairness -be able to identify and possibly mitigate bias in data collection and preprocessing, model and deployment (e.g. during visualisation of results)
Broader ethical and societal issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -identify and possibly minimise data science environmental impacts -understand the concept of ethics dumping during data collection and preprocessing -during the evaluation process, be able to take into consideration other factors besides accuracy, like <ul style="list-style-type: none"> --fairness --efficiency (in terms of resource allocation) --explainability --trustworthiness (as the qualitative measure of confidence one can objectively assign to the output of an AI system) --robustness outside the experimental settings whether the choices made during the project solve the initial problem, even if they provide accurate results.
Accountability and processes to ensure it	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -document each phase of the project by choosing and using existing documentation frameworks

Table 3 Expected learning outcomes for each Curriculum topic. The first column describes the topic, and the second one states what the trainee should be able to do after the completion of the programme.

3.4 Selection and Organisation of Content

The basic premise of the curriculum proposal is that we base the whole training on the CRISP-DM Model as described in [\(Shearer 2000\)](#).

The reasons that support this choice can be stated as follows:

- It is well-known and often used in data science projects.
- It has been developed mainly by industry. This is an advantage for a project like FAIR Data Spaces, which aims at collaboration between research and industry.
- It is already used to present ethical and legal issues in the different phases of the model and to develop frameworks that ensure the application of ethical standards in the development of data science projects. Specifically, (Saltz and Dewar 2019) conducted a systematic literature review and mapped the main ethical themes identified in the various phases of the CRISP-DM model. This paper was used as a basis for this proposal.

In the following subsections, we present the CRISP-DM model and approaches to use it for mapping ELSA subjects as presented in the bibliography and were used as an inspiration for the formation of this curriculum

3.4.1 The CRISP-DM Model

The CRISP-DM (CRoss-Industry Standard Process for Data Mining), is a non-proprietary, documented, and freely available industry-, tool-, and application-neutral model data mining model developed by industry leaders with input from more than 200 data mining users and data mining tool and service providers. It encourages best practices and offers organisations the structure needed to realise better and faster results. CRISP-DM comprises six phases: business understanding, data understanding, data preparation, modelling, evaluation, and deployment, which provide a road map to follow while planning and carrying out a data mining project (Shearer 2000).

Figure 1. The CRISP-DM Model. Image by Kenneth Jensen [CC BY-SA 3.0](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:CRISP-DM_Process_Diagram.png)
https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:CRISP-DM_Process_Diagram.png

[Figure 1](#) shows the phases of a data mining process. The arrows indicate the most important and frequent interactions and dependencies between the phases, while the outer circle symbolises the cyclical nature of the process itself. [Figure 2](#) shows the steps included in each phase.

Figure 2. Detailed description of CRISP-DM phases. Image by Nicole Leaper, [CC BY-NC-ND 3.0 US](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/3.0/us/), <https://exde.wordpress.com/2009/03/13/a-visual-guide-to-crisp-dm-methodology/>

3.4.2 Mapping Data Science Ethical Considerations to the CRISP-DM model

As mentioned above, the primary inspiration for the curriculum concept is (Saltz and Dewar 2019), where the authors perform a systematic literature review to map and describe the main ethical themes permeating data science. They go on to identify a possible structure to integrate these themes within a data science project in order to help data scientists cope more efficiently with the respective issues.

Similar approaches were followed (among others) by (Morley et al. 2020), who mapped to CRISP-DM existing Publicly Available AI Ethics Tools, Methods and Research to Translate Principles into Practices, i.e., moving from *What* to *How*, and the Turing Institute’s Guide for the responsible design and implementation of AI systems in the public sector (Leslie 2019). The

latter proposes an ethical platform for the responsible delivery of an AI project, focused primarily on CRISP-DM, but it can also be applied to other related workflow models. These two papers were also taken into consideration in the Curriculum formation.

(Saltz and Dewar 2019) codified their results in a framework to explore the key ethical considerations by project phase, as presented in [Table 4](#).

While their research identified four key themes, namely the need for an ethics framework, the newness of the field, data-related challenges, and model-related challenges, only two of them are important for our curriculum: Data and Model challenges.

Data-related challenges lead to the following ethical considerations: Privacy and anonymity, data misuse, and data accuracy and validity.

Model challenges lead to consideration of personal and group harm (e.g., discrimination resulting from algorithmic bias), subjective model design (e.g., the use of data points as proxies for missing facts), and model misuse and misinterpretation stemming from the statistical nature of predictive models and various degrees of transparency.

Regarding mapping the ethical considerations to the CRISP-DM model, the authors found no ethical theme related to the business understanding phase since this phase (focused mainly on accountability) presents no opportune subjects for a paper exploring new ethical issues relating to data science. Hence, they propose two new ethical considerations: Personal and group harm and team accountability.

Data-related challenges relate to the data understanding and data preparation phases, and model-related challenges relate to the modelling, evaluation, and deployment phases.

Based on this initial mapping, we will structure the ELSA Curriculum along the above-defined lines.

Project phase	Key ethical themes	Ethical considerations
Business understanding	Project initiation/ management challenges	Personal and group harm Team accountability
Data understanding/ data preparation	Data challenges	Data misuse Data privacy & anonymity Data accuracy

Modelling	Model challenges	Personal and group harm
Evaluation		Subjective model design
Deployment		Misuse/misinterpretation

Table 4. Framework to explore the key ethical considerations by phase of the project (Saltz and Dewar 2019)

3.4.3 Organization of Content: ELSA Curriculum for Data Scientists Modules

The curriculum structure has a vertical and a horizontal partition. There is a third dimension pertaining to the implementation of the curriculum and taking into consideration the feedback given for the first version as described in section [2 Feedback on the first version](#). This dimension concerns meeting the needs of different kinds of audiences, a subject deliberated in the first curriculum version but dealt more concretely here in section [3.5.1 Implementation Strategies](#).

The vertical one is expressed as modules that correspond to the CRISP-DM phases, while the horizontal one comprises knowledge units belonging to three strands that run through phases that correspond to the three topics areas detailed in [2.3 General topics outline](#).

[Figure 3](#) illustrates this vertical and horizontal partitioning.

Figure 3. Ethical and Societal, Legal and Technical Renderings Strands. With grey, we denote the ethical/societal strand, with light blue the legal strand, and with deep blue the technical renderings of the ELSA challenges.

The format followed for the description of each module is the following:

Module number and title: This always corresponds to a CRISP-DM model phase.

Phase description: Detailed description of the CRISP-DM phase as presented in (Shearer 2000) (the CRISP-DM model refers to *Data Mining*. We will replace this term with *Data Science*)

Knowledge Unit (KU) number and title

Description: Detailed description of the content.

Suggested activities: description of activities.

Module I: Business understanding

Phase description: This phase concerns understanding the project objectives from a business perspective, converting the problem to a data science problem, and devising the preliminary plan to achieve these objectives. (Saltz and Dewar 2019) identify the main ethical consideration for this phase as personal and group harm, i.e., the adverse impact of the application on individuals and/or groups, especially those already disadvantaged and/or marginalised.

KU I.1: Stakeholder identification

Stakeholders are defined as any group or individual that affects or is affected by the achievement of business objectives and their interactions with a corporation (Freeman 2010);

depending on the specific application, these might include shareholders and customers, the data scientist employed, the legal and HR departments or an organisation, marginalised groups, and the physical environment. Students are presented with a Typology of stakeholders in Data Science/AI and an explanation for each proposed type.

Suggested activities: The students are given examples of data science problem formulation and are asked to provide the stakeholders according to the presented typologies and the way the application might cause them harm. They are encouraged to think outside the typology if their assessment does not fit in the provided types

KU I.2: Incorporating community values

Data science as a profession lacks a specific certification that comes with the respective fiduciary duties and accountability. However, various national and international professional associations have issued professional codes that foster responsibility and advocate principles and values that enable data scientists to see themselves as a part of a community with specific expectations. In Germany, these include the Gesellschaft Für Informatik and the KI Bundesverband. Additionally, there is the development of the so-called “-by design” guidelines and frameworks: Ethics, Privacy, Data Protection, etc. Students are introduced to these frameworks and guidelines and the respective duties they impose.

Suggested activities: The students are given problems with ethical challenges and asked what their actions are before they are familiarised with the professional codes. They are then asked the same questions afterwards. They discuss whether being aware of the codes made any difference in their decisions and whether voluntary commitment to them is enough or if other measures must be taken.

KU I.3: Organisational culture

Organisational culture is an organisation’s systems, procedures, and practices for guiding and supporting ethical behaviour that clearly communicates the range of acceptable and unacceptable behaviours through leader role-modelling, reward systems, and rigorous code enforcement and is associated with fewer unethical decisions. Organisations that foster a climate that encourages employees to follow rules that protect the company and others when coping with ethical challenges are shown to be associated with fewer unethical decisions.

Suggested activities: Case studies of companies where poor (or debatable) organisational culture has provoked controversial ethical decisions.

KU I.4: Basic Legal Concepts

In order to establish a communication channel with other domain experts, such as legal scholars, the data scientists should be familiar with a number of basic concepts used by the experts mentioned above. These include basic legal concepts, such as domains of law and specifically of cyberlaw, law stratification (e.g. national vs international and EU law, and how

these relate), as well as concepts regarding accountability measures such as audit, impact assessment, compliance, risk assurance, etc.

Suggested activities: Case studies of data science applications where the manifestations of the above concepts are displayed.

Module II: Data Understanding

This phase concerns data collection, exploration, and quality verification, as well as gaining insights and identifying possible issues. (Saltz and Dewar 2019) identify the same issues for this and the following phase (i.e., Data preprocessing), which they collectively name as *data challenges* and specify as Data misuse, privacy & anonymity, and accuracy. While this might be adequate for identifying the general issues, we follow a more detailed approach by creating two different modules. The reason for that is that there are a number of challenges to be faced before any preprocessing takes place and that has to be underlined in the curriculum.

Additionally, this phase can alter the previous business understanding since data understanding can alter the initial problem definition. A third reason is that it might be the case that the same people do not perform phases 2 and 3, as data scientists may be provided with already existing datasets and are not directly connected with dataset creation. This is relevant in implementing the curriculum, as stated in the section [Implementation Strategies](#), as modules can be adapted to the target audience.

That said, a variety of issues are indeed common in both phases and can be addressed in either or both of them, as time and purpose constraints vary.

KU II.1: Data Protection

Data protection content is framed in the GDPR context. However, the goal is not to create a GDPR tutorial but to create familiarisation with the basic concepts and processes that relate to it. Additionally, data protection issues span through all the CRISP-DM phases, so the content may overlap or shift from one phase to another, depending on the implementation requirements.

In this phase are presented basic concepts and issues that have to do with data collection such as what is personal and sensitive data, data subject and their rights, data controller and data processor, the role of the DPO and legal grounds for processing personal data. Additionally, data protection goals based on the GDPR requirements are introduced in a suggested list linked to the SDM framework (cf. below in *Suggested activities*): Data minimisation, Availability, Integrity, Confidentiality, Unlinkability, Transparency and Intervenability. International data transfer is also covered, especially in conjunction with [KU II.4: Ethics dumping in data collection](#) and [KU III.4 Ethics dumping in data preprocessing](#)

Suggested activities: Illustration of the application of Data Protection in use cases via a framework, e.g. The Standard Data Protection Model(Unabhängiges Landeszentrum für Datenschutz 2020b; 2020a). The suggested framework can be used throughout the modules to illustrate appropriately chosen use cases. Reflection on how the data protection challenges can

change the problem definition and/or objectives as formed in the previous (*Business Understanding*) phase

KU II.2: Data bias during collection and ways to mitigate it

Bias is well documented in computer systems and specifically in data science applications. It has been in the spotlight from the very beginning, bringing up issues of justice, fairness, and discrimination, especially among sensitive and marginalised groups. Bias can be found in all the CRISP-DM phases, and in this KU special focus is given to historical and representation bias that are relevant in the data understanding phase and, more specifically, in data collection. Ways of detecting and mitigating data bias in this phase are also presented.

The use of synthetic data can also be investigated as a means to mitigate bias. Synthetic data creation and use can also be addressed in KUs about Ethics Dumping.

Suggested activities: Use Cases of historical and representation bias in data collection are presented, for example, in well known, publicly available image datasets. Practical exercises can be included where publicly available datasets and open source software that detects and mitigates bias in them are given to the students to experiment. The students are encouraged to reflect on how bias in data collection and bias mitigation might affect the other phases of application development, e.g., evaluation (regarding accuracy of results), deployment, and business understanding (problem definition and objectives). Also, they might examine alternative use cases of successful and unsuccessful use of synthetic data

KU II.3: Intellectual property issues and licences

This KU concentrates on the explanation of intellectual property challenges that govern data collection and understanding, specifically the licences that data come with, as well as the permissible ways to collect material, e.g. by scraping the internet.

Suggested activities: Students are presented with a use case and asked to identify possible IP problems; students are asked to scrape data from the internet, taking into consideration robots.txt files.

KU II.4: Ethics dumping in data collection

Ethics dumping is an issue found not only in data science but in other scientific domains as well. It can be defined as “the malpractice of (a) exporting research activities about digital processes, products, services, or other solutions, in other contexts or places (e.g. by European organisations outside the EU) in ways that would be ethically unacceptable in the context or place of origin and (b) importing the outcomes of such unethical research activities”(Floridi 2019). In our case, collecting data from countries that do not have the same safeguards regarding, for example, privacy or legally acquiring already existing datasets from such countries.

Synthetic Data can be seen as a method to overcome ethics dumping as well as challenges examined in the previous KUs (privacy, bias, IP). However, they come with their own issues of how appropriate they are for the specific problem and how they will be used in real world applications.

Suggested activities: Students are asked to reflect on the use of datasets obtained via ethics dumping and whether the practice, even if it is legal, means the continuing exploitation of vulnerable people not only in the Global South vs jeopardising their project because the inability to obtain similar data from their own more data protecting region (country or the EU).

KU II.5: Dataset documentation

Dataset documentation is very important, not only for identifying data provenance, data quality and validity, and IP licences but also for whether there is detected bias in the dataset and if some measure is taken in order to mitigate it. The students are presented with a number of data documentation suggestions, e.g. Datasheets for data sets, dataset nutrition labels, etc., and how to use them. Dataset documentation expands in the next phase as well.

Suggested activities: Apply some selected data documentation framework on a dataset, and students will be asked to reflect on the merits of the process vs. the overhead.

Module III: Data preparation

This phase aims to the construction of the final dataset that will be used by the model. It consists of selection of the actual data that will be used for the analysis task depending on the relevance of the project goals, quality and technical constraints, cleaning, construction integration and formatting of data. As noted in [Module II: Data Understanding](#) (Saltz and Dewar 2019) identify the same *data challenges* for both phases, namely, data misuse, privacy & anonymity, and accuracy. This is also reflected in the Curriculum since some KUs have the same titles; however, we try to differentiate between the relevant issues in either phase. The way that the continuity of the two phases could be implemented is discussed in [2.5.1 Implementation Strategies](#)

KU III.1: Data Protection

Further elaboration on the practical methods that the data protection goals described in [KU II.1: Data Protection](#). These two KUs can be covered as one continuous unit, starting with the basic definitions and concept introduction in [Module II: Data Understanding](#) and moving to more concrete examples in the present KU.

Suggested activities: Illustration of the application of Data Protection in use cases via a framework, e.g. The Standard Data Protection Model(Unabhängiges Landeszentrum für Datenschutz 2020b; 2020a)

KU III.2: Data challenges in preprocessing

Depending on the project, data preprocessing may include a variety of challenges, from annotation, cleaning, and creating synthetic data to choosing features and proxies, various kinds of bias (representation, measurement and aggregation bias) or even data validity issues (for example, a gap between the way annotation results between crowdsourcing and scholars' annotation, error induced by automatic machine learning annotation in the creation of synthetic data depending on the problem Outliers are sometimes relevant for data analysis). Solutions like bias identification and mitigation tools, as well as documentation practices, might be presented here as a continuation of the [KU II.2: Data bias during collection and ways to mitigate it](#) Ethics dumping is also an issue in this phase (annotation)

Suggested activities: Use cases of relevant bias can be presented and studied here, as well as Practical exercises can be included where publicly available datasets and open-source software that detects and mitigates bias in them are given to the students to experiment

KU III.3: Intellectual property issues of training data

Continuation of [KU II.3: Intellectual property issues and licences](#). These two KUs can be presented in both modules or in condensed form in either one of them.

This KU focuses on the different kinds of training data according to their licences when specifically considering generative AI issues: using copyrighted works in the training dataset, legally storing data for the training process, and copyright on the generated data, especially if we are talking about code. Provision of EU law on text and data mining (TDM) exception.

Suggested activities: Students are presented with a use case and asked to identify possible IP problems

KU III.4: Ethics dumping in data preprocessing

Ethics dumping in data preprocessing may comprise annotation and preprocessing activities outsourced to countries with lower standards in worker protection laws. This may include countries in the Global South, but not exclusively there. Ethics dumping can be considered in a broader sense here, such as using unqualified people to annotate data instead of experts because of lower costs. Thus, it is also related to the societal issues of worker exploitation and gig workers.

This unit could be taught in conjunction with the [respective one](#) in the previous module. The issue of synthetic data can also be addressed here since in their capacity to be produced from existing data can be regarded as a form of data preprocessing.

Suggested activities: Continue the previous module activity in the preprocessing phase. Reflect on how the data quality is affected by ethics dumping practices.

KU III.5: Dataset documentation

This KU is an extension of [KU II.4](#) for data preprocessing. These two KUs can be presented in both modules or in condensed form in either one of them. The students are presented with a number of data documentation suggestions, e.g. Datasheets for data sets, dataset nutrition labels, etc., and how to use them in order to document the preprocessing that has been done to the dataset regarding annotation, cleaning, bias detection and mitigation, etc.

Suggested activities: Continue the previous module activity in the preprocessing phase

Module IV: Modelling

This phase concerns the selection and parameter calibration of models according to the specific problem definition and specific data requirements. (Saltz and Dewar 2019) identify the ethical issues mainly around personal and group harm, specifically bias and discrimination. The curriculum addresses other issues as well in the following KUs:

KU IV.1: Model bias and mitigation techniques

Model bias can be identified in various forms, such as learning and aggregation bias as well as bias that can be found in pertained models and then transferred to the final trained model, which can lead to unfair outcomes and discrimination. The identification and mitigation of such kinds of bias are presented in this KU.

Suggested activities: Use cases of model bias can be presented and studied here, and practical exercises can be included where publicly available datasets and open source software that detects and mitigates bias in them are given to the students to experiment.

KU IV.2: Model transparency and explicability

Model transparency and explicability are covered in this KU not as technical issues, although a brief presentation of how well known models are positioned regarding these criteria might be advisable. The main focus is given on the ethical and legal (e.g. “right to explanation”) requirements of using transparent models. Particular focus is placed on the cases of automated decision making applications, where factors like automation bias are crucial in the discrimination of sensitive groups.

Suggested activities: The students are presented with use cases where opaque algorithms caused disparate negative impact. Practical exercises can be given when the same problem can be addressed with a number of different algorithms of various transparency.

KU IV.3: Environmental impact of model training

Model training may demand large amounts of energy. Depending on the way that this energy is produced, this may have grave environmental implications (e.g. increased carbon footprint). Various methods that calculate a model's environmental impact are presented, as well as the factors that determine their energy consumption.

Environmental impact issues can also be examined under the ethics dumping umbrella since the model training can be done in countries with lower environmental standards and then imported the outcomes (trained model). In that sense, this KU can be taught in conjunction with the respective ones in modules [II](#) and [III](#).

Suggested activities: The students are presented with examples of models and their energy consumption. Students are encouraged to reflect on the tradeoffs of environmental impact and application goals.

KU IV.4: Intellectual property issues

The use of pretrained models, commercial secrets, intellectual property of the trained model and the outcome of the algorithm. This KU concerns itself with intellectual property issues that pertain to the algorithm itself and its products. In that case, it can be linked to the deployment phase, corresponding to the [respective module](#). The content encompasses the latest advances in LLM and generative AI models, an area that is still not well developed (at the time of writing the present document). However, it contains important legal (and ethical) issues and, therefore, is included in the curriculum.

Suggested activities: The students are given case studies and asked to reflect on the limitations of IP regulation on product development and in broader subjects such as artistic creation.

KU IV.5: Model documentation

In correspondence with the dataset documentation, there are model documentation frameworks as well. Documenting the model is extremely important, especially when issues like bias and transparency are concerned. Model documentation frameworks (e.g. model cards) are presented.

Suggested activities: Students are asked to employ a model documentation framework for a made-up use case.

Module V: Evaluation

This process includes the review of the model construction and evaluation of whether it achieves the objectives set in the business understanding phase. (Saltz and Dewar 2019) identify as ethical considerations, subjective model design, i.e., various kinds of bias in the AI/ML pipeline and the inherent biases of the data scientists themselves, resulting in personal and group harm issues, are to be considered due to algorithmic discrimination. This Module addresses the issues of the tradeoff between algorithmic accuracy and a variety of other important factors, such as resource efficiency and trustworthiness. Specific focus is given to the concept of fairness, which is addressed in a KU of its own.

KU V.1: Evaluation beyond accuracy

Data science algorithms are usually evaluated with respect to their accuracy only. However, there are a number of other factors that have to be taken into consideration when we evaluate a model: fairness, efficiency (in terms of resource allocation, e.g. energy consumption as covered in [KU IV.3: Environmental impact of model training](#), but also the size of the model and the dataset), explainability (choosing a more transparent model as demonstrated in [KU IV.2: Model transparency and explicability](#) at the cost of less accurate results), trustworthiness (as the qualitative measure of confidence one can objectively assign to the output of an AI system, which includes apart from explainability robustness outside the experimental settings), whether the selected features and proxies actually solve the initial problem, although they provide accurate results. As per the CRISP-DM model, the evaluation phase might lead to reconsidering the problem definition (phase 1: Business understanding). This is not only meant as failing to accomplish the project goal but also as redefining the accuracy notion in order to incorporate the above mentioned issues.

Suggested activities: Students are given use cases and are encouraged to reconsider the project goal with respect to the above described issues. Practical exercises are also possible in conjunction with the next KU dealing with fairness.

KU V.2: Fairness

The bias and discrimination that may result in a data science application are dealt with in the previous modules, where they are examined at specific data science circle phases. However, it is often that the evaluation phase indicates plainly whether such issues are present; in the previous phases, we act proactively and, while checking in advance is needed, it is not always possible to grasp all the implications. The evaluation phase gives us a first tangible result we can use to assess whether there are such issues present (the other being the deployment phase, of course).

In this KU, the various definitions of fairness and how these are mathematically formulated and executed in code. There is also a description of the legal provisions in the EU regarding fairness and the human perceptions of it and how these impact the trustworthiness of a product, as well as insights from other disciplines (e.g., ethical philosophy) that go beyond technical solutions.

Suggested activities: Practical exercises where the students are asked to apply various fairness definitions in coding sessions and assess the results.

KU V.3: Model documentation

This is a continuation of the previous phase KU of the same name. All evaluation metrics used to assess the model and the respective results are documented according to a specific documentation model.

Suggested activities: Students are asked to employ a model documentation framework for a made-up use case.

Module VI: Deployment

This phase includes deployment, monitoring and maintenance of the system. Even though it is often the customer who carries out the deployment steps, it is important for the customer to understand how they actually use the system and its limitations. As (Saltz and Dewar 2019) point out, the data scientist's ethical responsibilities do not end with the completion of a project. The data scientist also has a duty to explain their choices and the implications using language that non data scientists, such as managers, can understand.

KU VI.1: System deployment limitations

The data scientist must be able to explain to the clients, managers and project stakeholders (as identified in [KU I.1: Stakeholder identification](#)), the system limitations, both with respect to known issues and with what the system is actually able to do or not, and also explain the chosen level of automation and the possible impact that these might have, especially in the case of adverse outcomes.

Suggested activities: The students are given use cases that illustrate individual and group harms that specific systems caused because they were deployed without the proper understanding of their abilities and limitations. They are encouraged to provide suggestions of how proper communication to the stakeholders of the application limitations would have averted these harmful consequences.

KU VI.2: Visualisation bias

This specific kind of bias is addressed in this phase, since most visualisation is used to convey results to the final system users. Since most data science applications provide results of statistical nature, there are a number of well known pitfalls that exist when trying to visualise them; however, data scientists are not especially familiar with them as they are usually thought of as UX issues. An introduction in the subject will help data scientists to fruitfully cooperate with UX designers in order to avoid as much as possible misinterpretation of results.

Suggested activities: The students are given use cases where visualisation bias is present and they are asked to reflect on possible ways to avoid it.

KU VI.3: Accountability and processes to ensure it

This is a mirror image of some of the subjects dealt with in [Module I: Business understanding](#) where addressed issues like auditing frameworks and organisation culture and processes, the extent of personal responsibility and the case for certification for data scientists in conjunction with professional codes and the creation of a formal profession.

Suggested activities: The students are exposed to auditing frameworks and are asked to apply them to a use case.

[Figure 4](#). Shows a more detailed, albeit not exhaustive, presentation of the Curriculum content. Each of these blobs may correspond to more than one knowledge unit; some of the topics addressed in each module can be seen in the figure.

To the original three strands, we added a documentation knowledge unit that runs through all modules, emphasising the need to document each action taken during the various phases of the project. The way of doing this depends on the phase; we do not advocate for a specific documentation or auditing system; we merely present existing options for each phase, such as model cards.

A summary table for all KUs can be found in [Appendix I](#)

Business Understanding	Data Understanding	Data Preparation	Modelling	Evaluation	Deployment
Stakeholder identification	Data challenges: Bias and mitigation, synthetic data, annotation, cleaning, minimization, (pseudo)anonymization		Model bias and mitigation, transparency and explicability	Evaluation beyond accuracy	Visualisation bias
Incorporating community values				Fairness	
Organisational culture	Ethics dumping				System deployment limitations
Basic legal concepts	Data Protection		Environmental impact of model training		Accountability and processes to ensure it
	Intellectual property				
Documentation					

Figure 4. A detailed presentation of the Curriculum. Not all KUs are represented; rather, the main subjects are addressed. In Figure 3, grey denotes the ethical/societal strand, light blue the legal strand, and deep blue the technical renderings of the ELSA challenges.

3.5 Means of Content Delivery: Selection and Organization of the Learning Experience

3.5.1 Implementation Strategies

The implementation strategy followed to apply the Curriculum depends on the resources, time given, and target audience.

The ELSA Curriculum is intended for data science practitioners, i.e., people who are already employed in various data science projects. This is a varied and not homogenous group as demonstrated in [Section 3.2 Need Diagnosis](#), as it may consist of people having various levels of experience both in data science and exposure to ELSA challenges. Additionally, they may be fulfilling a variety of roles, ranging from programmers who only implement specific pieces of code to system architects and project managers.

The application field is also very important to consider: implementing a data science project for marketing presents different challenges than one in health care.

In its conception, the Curriculum tries to assume a generic audience with little knowledge of ELSA issues in data science projects. However, we recognise that this is seldom the case.

We propose the following implementation strategies:

1. **Introductory course assuming little or no knowledge of ELSA:** This course is targeted to new professionals, or to professionals who never had any education or experience regarding ELSA issues. These may be either people who have just finished their studies or moving into data science from another discipline and have no background in ELSA issues.

As we have seen in the landscape description and the profile of the data scientist(Christoforaki 2022), very few academic institutions offer ELSA courses, so it is expected that fresh graduates do not have an ELSA background from their studies. People who come to data science from other disciplines may have a tertiary education degree or not, in which case they may have arrived in data science via non-formal education (like online courses or self-study). To those, we may include data scientists who originate from countries outside the one where they presently work (Germany in our case) and are not knowledgeable about the current working environment and its ELSA requirements (for example, EU Data protection laws). The purpose of the instruction program in this case, is to raise awareness of ELSA issues and enhance sensibility to them, as well as offering general knowledge to be used as a roadmap when encountering such issues. In this configuration, all the presented modules are taught in an intensive course akin to a university course with a shorter duration (1-2 months) and more hours (2-3 hours per day).

2. **Selection of modules that fit the roles of the target audience:** As shown in the Landscape description (Christoforaki 2022), we can distinguish between two kinds of data scientists: one with mastery of maths, statistics and visualisation techniques, including some social science research methods skills –such as the ability to raise the appropriate questions and hypothesis–, as well as soft skills associated with communication and teamwork and a second one with computer science and programming skills. The first category might benefit more from an in-depth study of some modules (for example, Business Understanding and Deployment) or some knowledge units within modules (for example, legal KUs), while the second category from deep

dives into technical renderings of ELSA issues within modules. This approach does not exclude any KUs but provides more advanced content with respect to the target audience's needs and preferences.

3. **Adaptation of the content according to the application domain that interests the target audience:** While a general awareness of ELSA challenges can be applied to all application domains, there are some applications that necessitate a special approach. For example, the development of Health Care data science applications has specific and strong demands regarding the Data Protection issues. Additionally, there is variance regarding the technical renderings that make sense, for example, in NLP vs Image processing applications. Whenever possible, it might be desirable to focus on the application domain the target audience works in, for example, proposing relevant use cases or practical exercises.
4. **A combination of points 2. and 3.** This means that the modules will be highly specialised in terms of both the application domain and the role of the audience members. That might call for specific curriculum implementations, which could include only some of the modules or knowledge units within each module and can either contain more specialised knowledge with a shorter duration than in the general curriculum coverage or both. These can lead to the development of advanced programs aimed at specific professionals.

Specifically, we distinguish between four kinds of modules:

1. **Core modules:** These modules concern basic knowledge regarding ELSA issues in data science. They provide the essential competencies a data scientist must have and target young professionals or professionals who have never had any education or experience regarding ELSA issues. These modules are the basis which other modules can be added to. Data scientists who have acquired this basic knowledge through experience or in their studies can skip these modules. However, it would be advisable to take a test to check whether they are actually familiar with all the concepts presented there. All the other arrangements presented below presuppose that the trainees have attained the basic knowledge provided by the core module either by following a training program or by accumulated work experience. The preferred format for this kind of training would be a Summer or Winter school (intensive course of 1-2 weeks). These modules include [KU I.2: Incorporating community values](#), [KU I.4: Basic Legal concepts](#), Data protection ([KU II.1](#), [KU III.1](#)), Bias ([KU II.2](#), [KU III.2](#), [KUI V.1](#)) and documentation modules ([KU II.5](#), [KU III.5](#), [KU IV.5](#), [KU V.3](#)), [KU V.1: Evaluation beyond accuracy](#), [KU V.2: Fairness](#), [KU VI.1: System deployment limitations](#).
2. **Role-specific modules:** As noted in point 2 above, not all data scientists are implicated in all the phases of the project pipeline. Depending on their role in a project, they may opt for deep dives into specific knowledge areas, such as data protection, stakeholder identification, or data understanding and preparation challenges. The preferred format for this kind of training would be workshops on specific topics (2-3 days maximum). The

modules that can constitute each program could be assembled according to the interests of the participants. For example, for project managers, a possible assortment might include KU I.1: Stakeholder identification, KU I.2: Incorporating community values, KU VI.1: System deployment limitations, Dataset and model documentation models (KUs II.5, III.5, IV.5 and V.3) and KU VI.3: Accountability and processes to ensure it.

3. **Domain-specific modules:** These modules target specific application domain professionals, such as healthcare, NLP, or image processing. Their content could be the adaptation of the generic modules to the challenges of the specific application or technical domain. For example, for healthcare, there can be deep dives into KU II.1 and II.1 Data protection specifically for health care as well as KU I.1 Stakeholder identification and KU IV.2 Model transparency and explicability. Regarding NLP modules like KU II.3 and III.3 on intellectual property of training data and KUs regarding bias (data, model and visualisation) might be suggested. The preferred format for this kind of training would be workshops on specific topics (2-3 days maximum).
4. **A combination of 2 and 3** could also be possible, for example, a Half-day workshop about intellectual property issues for project managers or a 2-3 days Workshop about identification and mitigation of data and model bias for technical directors and/or developers in healthcare chatbot development.

3.5.2 Classroom Techniques

In this section, we will focus on two aspects: who should teach and the choice of learning experiences that can be used to implement the curriculum, i.e., the format that would be most effective in imparting the learning objectives to the trainees, being workshops, lectures, group work, etc.

Who should teach

The nature of the curriculum is interdisciplinary, so there is a need for a variety of domain experts (some highly specialised) to cooperate and teach the respective KUs. However, they should always keep in mind that the purpose of the program is to raise ELSA awareness and provide the participants with the means to communicate effectively with the domain experts, not to turn them into ones. Tutors must always have in mind that while the material is multifaceted, containing ethical, legal, societal and technical strands, the focus is always on how a data scientist would be able to cope with it. While we admit that this provides a challenging environment for both instructors and program participants, we hope and believe that the mere coexistence and cooperation between different domains of expertise will benefit both of them. An example of a multidisciplinary course that can be used as a guide can be found in (Reich et al. 2020).

The Choice of Learning Experiences (LE) and Course Formats

Learning Experiences (LE) are defined by (Via et al. 2020) as “any setting or interaction in or via which learning takes place: e.g., a lecture, game, exercise, role-play, etc.”. They define the following LEs: lecture, webinar, practical exercise, flipped class, peer instruction, group discussion, group work and problem-solving. [Table 5](#) below summarises the definitions and the teaching targets that each LE facilitates.

LE	Definition	Teaching targets facilitated
Lecture/webinar	a didactic approach in which oral presentation is used to describe & explain concepts and impart facts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Inspire learners and ignite learners' enthusiasm ● clarify/explain a concept ● provide an overview, give context, and summarise content
Practical exercise	an activity to put into practice learned skills & knowledge, generally in a lab setting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Help learners digest course materials, ● solve typical problems, ● apply knowledge, ● show how to do things with appropriate guidance, ● give an idea of how a tool works
Flipped class	a learner-centred approach in which students are introduced to new topics prior to class; class time is then used to explore those topics in greater depth via interactive activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Teach learners how to formulate questions, ● help learners to memorise new information and concepts or analyse and understand course materials
Peer instruction	an interactive, in-class, learner-centred approach in which groups of two or more students briefly discuss a question or assignment given by the instructor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Prepare learners to defend an argument, ● Give learners opportunities to explain things,

LE	Definition	Teaching targets facilitated
		thereby helping to develop critical thinking and awareness
Group discussion	an in-class, learner-centred approach in which students discuss ideas, solve problems &/or answer questions, guided by the instructor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Give learners opportunities to practice questioning, develop new ideas & critical thinking
Group work	a learner-centred approach in which students are organised into groups (& perhaps assigned specific roles) & are given tasks to perform collaboratively	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote collaborative work & peer instruction, • provide opportunities for giving/receiving feedback, & digesting course materials
Problem- solving	a learner-centred approach in which students are required to systematically investigate a problem by building or determining the best strategy to solve it (using what is known to discover what is not known)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote learner abilities to identify & evaluate solutions, develop new ideas, make decisions, evaluate decision effectiveness, troubleshoot

Table 5. Learning Experiences' definitions and targets according to (Via et al. 2020)

(Engelhardt 2022) identifies the following LEs: lectures, workshops, events, online courses, self-learning material, and training interventions. However, we observe that these could be better described as course formats than LEs (with the exception of lectures and webinars/online courses, which are common in both taxonomies). A workshop, for example, may include both lectures and practical exercises, an event group discussion, etc. In the following table, we adapt the descriptions of the LEs and the pros and cons that the authors present regarding them as course formats. [Table 6](#), below presents the course format characteristics, pros and cons according to Engelhardt (2022)

Course Format	Characteristics	Pros	Cons
Lectures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • traditional form of teaching/training is an effective way to provide basic information about 	–Great delivery format for experienced and motivated learners	–Could be time-consuming –Learner engagement is key.

Course Format	Characteristics	Pros	Cons
	<p>the topic</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • can be recorded and used as flipped classroom material combined with an interactive workshop • basic concepts of a topic can be communicated effectively through brief lectures • can include discussions, other activating methods and hands-on exercises after the lecture to consolidate the key points of learning 	<p>–Possibility to fully incorporate content in any existing course.</p>	
Workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • can be organised around a certain topic, or they can be more general in scope • an opportunity to find out and discuss the main questions or problems your target audience has • organisers can also provide standard offerings that will be repeated every year and plan for add-on workshops that would vary from year to year to meet the specific needs of the audience 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ideal for delivering single-topic content or for a targeted group; • Flexible, short and easy to organise. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To cover all topics a workshop series may be required; • Learners might miss out on important topics due to self-selection biases.
Events	<p>A good way to influence these types of audiences is to raise awareness with brief presentations</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Most suitable for promotional purposes; 	<p>–Limited time;</p> <p>–Messages need to be clear and concise.</p>

Course Format	Characteristics	Pros	Cons
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Great for networking; • Ideal to provide information for follow-up services and/or direct links to access existing materials. 	<p>–ideal ways to provide information about future training offerings or to direct attendees to self-learning materials</p>
Online courses	<p>–a convenient way to organise training for a large number of participants or for participants from many locations</p> <p>–they can be taught fully online without any live interactions (asynchronous online learning), as a course where live training is given (synchronous online learning), or as a combination of the two</p>	<p>–Flexible, self-paced, independent.</p> <p>–Easy to manage and update at the back-end with minimal impact on learner experiences</p>	<p>–Need to be aware of issues of student retention in asynchronous learning;</p> <p>–Lack of live interactions and low engagement;</p> <p>–Could include weekly or bi-weekly live office hours to include partial synchronous learning;</p> <p>–Use interactive course content to facilitate learner engagement.</p>
Self-learning material	<p>–an important part of any training format.</p> <p>–this material is a reference for learners to consult as a recommended information source after a course or</p>	<p>–Could be used and referenced in conjunction with other training formats;</p> <p>–Could be used by learners, teachers, trainers, and research</p>	<p>–Passive learning;</p> <p>–not easy to track learning progress and outcomes;</p> <p>–need to pay attention to the organisation and</p>

Course Format	Characteristics	Pros	Cons
	<p>event.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – can also be used separately to acquire the basics or to check a certain fact. –materials created by other parties can also be used 	support staff as references.	maintenance of the most up-to-date information in self-learning materials.
Training interventions	Occurs in situations where the level of stakeholders' knowledge does not meet their everyday needs and training activity is undertaken by the individual in order to equip [them] with the wherewithal for performance at the required level	–a great way to keep in touch with the research community and to effectively meet stakeholders' needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –operates on a case-by-case basis, which could prove to be a time-consuming task if you need to reach all the stakeholders –could render the service model unscalable, especially if operating with a very small service provision team

Table 6. Course formats and their characteristics, pros and cons according to (Engelhardt 2022).

For the curriculum implementation, we can employ a variety of classroom techniques that are fitting to the specific KUs. These can range from lectures, invited talks and case studies to cooperative learning techniques like student workgroups and role-playing to practical exercises where students are asked to write code, for example, detecting data bias in given datasets. At the description of the landscape deliverable (Christoforaki 2022), our review leads us to the conclusion that the students evaluated more positively practical exercises and use-case studies (an example illustrating how the FAIR Data Spaces demonstrators can be employed as use cases is given in section [3. Case Studies: The FAIR-DataSpaces Demonstrators](#) of the present document), as well as engagement activities like discussion and debates based on real-world cases provided via public media (newspaper articles, videos, news, etc). While lectures can impart a large amount of knowledge in a small amount of time with not very demanding resources, they also have the lowest evaluation assessment with respect to their effectiveness.

3.5.3 Resources for Implementing the Knowledge Units

The material used in the Curriculum implementation is to be decided by the instructors of each KU. It can be adapted according to the implementation strategy chosen as described in [2.5.1 Implementation Strategies](#) and must be updated since new issues develop constantly, as well as methods to tackle them, most notably in the legal and technical rendering strands.

3.6 Evaluation

The evaluation issue is twofold: how to evaluate the participants and how to evaluate the curriculum and the program implementation.

The first one depends on the implementation selected strategy. The participants could be evaluated by their engagement in the various modules, for example, by participation and application of the knowledge acquired in Use Cases via the organisation of Hands-On workshop sessions during the study program that implements the Curriculum.

This can be differentiated according to the objective of the program implementation, e.g. awareness or creating competencies in specific domains (e.g. bias detection and mitigation).

Regarding the program, the usual way is to get feedback both from the participants and the instructors on whether the program fulfilled their expectations or not. In this sense, the best way to evaluate the curriculum is the implementation of a pilot instruction program, followed up with a detailed evaluation via participants' and tutors' evaluation sheets, or interviews. However, this is not in the scope of the FAIR Data Spaces project.

4. The FAIR-DataSpaces Demonstrators as Case Studies

In the context of the FAIR Data Spaces project, three demonstrators have been developed: a. for a biodiversity data space, b. research data quality assurance, and c. cross-platform data analytics. These three demonstrators are proposed as *Use Cases for the ELSA Curriculum*. For this purpose, we used input from the AP2 "*Rechtliche und ethische Rahmenbedingungen*" work package regarding the Legal and Ethical Review of the Demonstrators and specifically from "E2.2.1: Bericht Vertragsrechtliche Überprüfung und Compliance" project deliverable (Breß et al. 2023).

In the following sections we will present: a. A brief description of each demonstrator and b. How the demonstrator can be considered as a Use Case for the ELSA data science curriculum.

4.1 Biodiversity Demonstrator

The first demonstrator on biodiversity has as the main software component Geo Engine. It is a cloud-based research environment for spatio-temporal data processing, supporting interactive data analyses for geodata (such as vector and raster data), that allows data scientists to focus on the actual data analyses rather than data preparation.

In the context of the FAIR-Data Spaces project, Geo Engine adds new data connectors and cloud features to demonstrate important aspects of FAIR-DS, including novel use cases which combine data from a variety of sources as well as authentication according to GAIA-X specifications('WP3 WP4 Technical Foundations and Demonstrators', n.d.).

Technical description

Geo Engine consists of a backend and two frontends: `geoengine-ui` for Web and `geoengine-python` library(Beilschmidt, et al. 2023).

The backend handles data access, data management and query execution and provides APIs for the frontends and third-party applications and consists of three modules:

- **data types:** contains the primitives for vector and raster data as well as basic operations and spatial projections
- **operators:** contains the spatiotemporal query execution engine and the implementation of operators
- **Services:** contains the data management, e.g., adding, updating and removing datasets, workflows and projects, and Web APIs on top of this functionality. It can also handle user management, authentication via OpenIDConnect single sign-on (SSO) providers, and authorization, which allows restricting access to resources such as data and workflows to certain users and groups.

The main output of Geo Engine is layers of spatio-temporal data: either feature collections or raster images.

Geo Engine can access internal and external data. Loadable data is identified by an ID used by an input operator to resolve the necessary loading information(e.g., name, location, and the used spatial projection) using a metadata provider. Internal data are stored as datasets in a database. Users can create their own datasets and share them with other users. External data is provided by Data Providers who have to allow browsing and access to data not managed by Geo Engine. In contrast to local datasets, external data cannot be edited or deleted, and the available data may change over time.

The Web frontend `geoengine-ui` consists of three parts:

-
- a core library: provides a client implementation for the backend API services, e.g. for managing layers and building block components like the map, plots, and operator dialogues
 - a GIS application: offers the full functionality of Geo Engine, which is targeted at expert users who can work with multiple layers, apply operators and review workflow graphs
 - multiple apps and dashboards: simpler applications that focus on a concrete use case and only require access to a few selected inputs

While the demonstrator is offered in the cloud, in contrast to previous systems, which are operated by cloud providers such as Amazon or Google and prevent the exchange of data between individual providers, this system is intended to explicitly promote such an exchange and prevent a so-called vendor lock-in. The system implemented for this purpose is to be open source and expandable in order to be able to take into account the specific needs of individual users with regard to data protection and data security.

However, data sovereignty over the data used is maintained. Access is not universal but can be restricted for certain user groups to consider legal frameworks of the data

Application example

As a Geo Engine application, we can examine the use case of a forester who wants to survey the health status of forest trees. To do that, they have to follow a temporal development, for example, comparing the condition of the vegetation in the same month over several years to detect changes that might entail possible measures.

Geo Engine can be used to display the location data of trees on a map in the web browser to which satellite images can be added for analysis, which can lead to measures initiated by experts. For example, the felling of trees due to a beetle infestation.

Ethical and legal concerns exemplified

The Geo Engine demonstrator can be used to exemplify concerns regarding the collection and processing of personal data. Although the demonstrator is not aimed to be used with personal data, it uses a wide range of data that are aggregated and combined with geolocation. A possible subject that can be tackled is the consideration of how exactly the processing of personal data is prevented and how any liability for misuse of the demonstrator via illegitimate processing of personal data might be avoided. One possible approach is to demonstrate how to communicate clearly to potential users the restrictions on the functionality in relation to personal data, as well as, in terms of use, exclusion of liability on the part of the service provider - whoever this is - relating to any illegitimate choice to process personal data. Specifically, in (Breß et al. 2023) can be found detailed presentations of the process flow and the role distribution regarding the provisions of GDPR (3.2.1.1 Vorgangsserien and 3.2.1.2

Datenschutzrechtliche Rollenverteilung, respectively), while possible issues like Privacy by design are also addressed.

Intellectual property, copyright, patent, and trade secrecy issues can be addressed to protect a) the data entering the demonstrator, b) the demonstrator's results, and c) the demonstrator itself (Breß et al. 2023).

While the use case presented has to do with forest surveillance, a possible application might be surveillance of a disease, for example, malaria or HIV and its spread in different parts of the world. This might introduce considerations regarding bias and stigmatisation not of individuals only (if we accept that no personal data is held by the system), but of whole countries and regions that may be negatively characterised. This fact can reflect badly on the individual inhabitants of these areas which can lead to discrimination when, for example, these people travel to other countries by border authorities. This can be extrapolated to generalisations used by extremists for political purposes, especially when coupled with race or vulnerable status (e.g. refugees).

4.2 Data Validation and Quality Assurance

This demonstrator's purpose is to demonstrate the use of decentralised task runners to perform automated quality control and data assurance within a commonly available or easily provided environment.

Within the FAIR Data Spaces project it is aimed to develop a GAIA-X compatible demonstrator that leverages the hardware sources provided with the Open Telecom Cloud and allows a theoretical research group to provide simple information about the data they intend to collect. When data is added to local or cloud-based storage, this information is used to ensure that each new file matches the specified data schemas and to monitor those files for unusual or unexpected values. The demonstrator also ingests these data files to create three types of simple web-based reports that allow users to view simple summary data without having to access the individual data files

Technical description

The demonstrator consists primarily of a Python library, which contains all the code necessary to run the analysis. Also provided are a publicly available GitLab repository, which contains a CI/CD script that automatically calls the library and can be customised to the user's use case, and a Docker Container that comes preinstalled with the library and all dependencies needed to execute it. ('WP3 WP4 Technical Foundations and Demonstrators', n.d.)

The demonstrator is not intended for use with restricted access or sensitive data sets but has an authentication process that does provide some security with respect to data access.

The repository is available under an open-source licence.

Application example

A use case can be designed as follows:

Researchers aim to monitor crop yields, in order to determine what particular growing conditions and what crop varieties do best. For that reason, they:

- recruit a large group of farmers willing to participate in a semi-annual survey conducted in person via a web form
- Ingest fine-grained weather data provided through a publicly available API.

It is important that this data is properly cleaned and cleared of collection anomalies for later analysis.

Users must provide the repository (run within the GitLab installation at RWTH Aachen University), with access credentials and, at the beginning of the project, schema files in a frictionless data format that describe the table format of their survey data and weather data, including value types, expected value ranges, and field validation patterns. In addition, they can use these schema files to provide metadata about each field in the form of brief explanations.

As surveys are collected, the demonstrator is scheduled to run every night and process any new or updated files. If, for example, it discovers that the surveyor accidentally recorded the date in a format that does not match the one specified in the schema file, this is flagged in the error report and can be corrected immediately before it is included in any further analysis.

The same procedure is followed for automatically created or downloaded data.

In both cases, users are quickly alerted to a quality problem in their data, as when the report is generated, it triggers an email to members of the repository indicating those problems while the report is posted on a website so that all members of the project can see and fix those problems. The report also includes a collection of summary statistics so that users can perform a cursory analysis of each data file.

Ethical and legal concerns exemplified

This demonstrator can be used to exemplify intellectual property issues, such as trade secrecy rights (trade secrets) and copyright.

Regarding copyright, (Breß et al. 2023), describe the relevant laws and explain how the Data Quality Assurance Demonstrator can be used how the issue of the short-term copying of data as part of quality control could be addressed.

In the case of the specific demonstrator, a copyright issue can be identified when the data are duplicated for quality control by the algorithm. This right belongs in principle to the creator alone

as the holder of copyright; however, the author can also grant certain rights to third parties, if necessary comprehensively, while actions that infringe copyright may be permitted by other justifications, for example, for scientific research, albeit presumably to a rather limited extent.

Furthermore, the data manipulated by the demonstrator might also contain trade secrets or be under patent.

So, the demonstrator can be used in order to exemplify to the trainees:

- The notion of copyright vs trade secret vs patent
- What kinds of works are eligible for copyright protection
- Who is considered to be the copyright holder
- What actions can be considered copyright infringement and what are the consequences of such actions
- When reproduction of copyrighted data may be justified
- What constitutes a trade secret
- What Are infringements of patent law

Regarding ethical issues related to intellectual property, a suitable subject would be FAIR vs FRAND principles. The issue is dealt with in detail in (Breß et al. 2023). To summarise:

The FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) principles, exemplified in the present project, make datasets more sustainable and effective by facilitating data reusability, ensuring that data is accessible not only to humans but also to machines, and promoting transparency, reproducibility, and reusability.

FRAND (fair, reasonable, and non-discriminatory), on the other hand, refers to when owners of standard essential patents grant third parties the use of their rights on fair, reasonable, and non-discriminatory terms before adopting a standard.

Since standard development has a great impact on economic development as well as everyday life, it is important to understand how FAIR and FRAND are related. Overall, FRAND and FAIR can be seen as part of a broader trend that aims to promote openness, collaboration and fairness in technology and science, where intangible assets are used in a way that is both equitable and beneficial to society as a whole, creating a digital world that is both innovative and inclusive.

4.3 Cross-Platform FAIR Data Analysis

The third demonstrator uses a federated learning-based platform called PHT(Personal Health Train), which operates on Health care data (e.g. hospital data) and its basic characteristic is that

since it operates on sensitive data, ensures privacy and data governance by keeping the cloud-based data spaces separate from hospital data silos, which are only accessed by local clients.

Technical description

Since the technical implementation of PHT is quite complex, here, we describe the basic architecture and workflow. A more technical description can be found in (Jaberansary et al. 2023).

The PHT concept originates from an analogy from the real world, specifically from the railway system. The basic elements are trains, stations, and train depots:

- The train uses the network to visit different stations and contains specific analysis tasks, which are executed at distributed data nodes (the Stations); they move from Station to Station to consume data as an outcome of the executed analytical task.

The results are incrementally generated and can be anything based on the Train code. For example, the result set can contain data on an aggregated level, for example, a number showing a cohort size, which has no relationship to individual patient data of the input level, or updated parameters of a statistical model, such as a regression model that is incrementally fitted from Station to Station.

- Stations hold confidential data and execute analytic tasks; hence, they have two main components:
 - The data source: A Station can hold the data itself or provide an access point to the sensitive data.
 - Station software: The main task of the Stations is executing the containerised analytic algorithms. They can also reject requests if the Station admin has doubts about the data usage or a lack of capacity. After the task is completed, the results are inspected and can be rejected if the result set contains confidential information.
- The depot is represented by the Central Service (CS), which includes procedures for Train orchestration, operational logic, business logic, and data management.(Welten et al. 2022). The Central Services are responsible for coordinating the execution of the analysis on the distributed data sources within the data space.

Figure 3. High-level Architecture of the PHT Infrastructure for the Demonstrator (Jaberansary et al. 2023)

A workflow in PHT (as illustrated in Fig 3. and described in (Jaberansary et al. 2023)) goes like this:

- First, the Station admin pulls and decrypts the Train (analytical task, in this example, a classification of patient record images).
- The Station admin provides connection information to the data source.
- In the initial phase of the analytical task, existing patient resources in the training set are queried to obtain clinical data and related image references (URLs). The dataset is then divided into training and test datasets. Typically, the ratio is 80:20.
- Based on the referenced URLs, the analysis task downloads the corresponding images from a server. A classification model is trained using both data types. The existing derived model weights directly update the previous model trained in earlier stations. The test dataset is used to evaluate the accuracy of the model. Such monitor data is saved and used later for inspection and feedback.
- Finally, the Train image is saved with the new results (updated classification model) and then returned to the Train repository in the central service.

Application example

The application use case concerns Skin Lesion Detection. The dataset is accessible via three different PHT stations and consists of structured clinical data (including age and gender) and, mainly, image data showing different kinds of skin lesions; each image shows one snapshot of one type of (labelled) skin lesion. Apart from the cloud-based station, the two other stations use on-premise infrastructures, which allows the data providers (hospitals in this case) full control of their data.

The analysis aims to train a classification model to predict the skin lesion type of new images of potentially unknown persons. In order to achieve this aim, the process follows the workflow described in the previous section, where the algorithm that creates the trained model is loaded on a train that stops at each station, is executed and moves on to the next station. In the end, the trained model arrives to the original researcher who asked it and can be used to identify skin lesions in new images. In the process, no personal or sensitive data is moved around, and the data providers exercise full control over their data, revealing as much or as little of it as they wish.

Ethical and legal concerns exemplified

PHT aims to provide a system suitable for scientific analyses of sensitive data stored in multiple locations without the data itself ever leaving the storage locations. This stems from its application domain (health care) and the increased sensitivity regarding the treatment of sensitive personal data. The system can be used to exemplify the challenges regarding personal data in general and specifically in the healthcare domain, as well as how the approach of PHT (federated learning) can be used to avoid adverse outcomes. Additionally, it can be used as an example of privacy by design architecture.

However, it can also be used to exemplify the issues posed by opaqueness regarding the data; since the end user does not have any access to them, so they are not aware of any issues that might exist, for example, underlying biases, either in the original data or the preprocessed data that are made available from each provider. The system is practically a black box where the only result that the end user sees is the trained model, but does not have any inkling about the data used to produce that outcome. A possible solution is to apply proper documentation regarding the characteristics of the dataset so even if the data itself is not available for scrutiny, the metadata regarding the dataset characteristics are. This will enable the end user (researcher) to understand the nature of the dataset, anticipate and mitigate potential issues (e.g. bias), and correctly interpret the results.

Another issue that this demonstration can exemplify is the problems induced by incremental learning like catastrophic forgetting (i.e., neural networks gradually forgetting previously learned information (French 1999)), or the fact that the order the Train follows has an impact on the results. While both of these issues seem purely technical, they can induce various ethical

issues, such as the impact of diverging results on the analysis and, in the end, the patients when the results are deployed.

5. Conclusions

This report presents the second and final version of an ELSA Curriculum for data scientists. For the compilation of this report, we took into consideration the feedback given in workshops and surveys we conducted after the publication of the first version of the ELSA Curriculum both as a Zenodo report (Christoforaki 2023) and a scientific paper (Christoforaki and Beyan 2024).

The basic premise of the curriculum structure is that it must follow the CRISP-DM model and employ material organised in Knowledge Units (KUs) belonging to three strands: ethical and societal, legal, and technical rendering subjects.

In this final version, we also expanded the means of delivery section to include a flexible implementation approach depending on the target audience.

Finally, the three demonstrators of the FAIR Data Spaces project are presented as use cases that can be employed in an instruction program, each one exemplifying a variety of ethical, legal and societal aspects.

References

- Beauchamp, Tom L, and James F Childress. 2019. *Principles of Biomedical Ethics*. 8th ed. Beilshmidt, Christian, Dröner, Johannes, Mattig, Michael, Schweitzer, Philip, and Seeger, Bernhard. 2023. 'Geo Engine: Workflow-Backed Geo Data Portals'. <https://doi.org/10.18420/BTW2023-55>.
- Breß, Constantin, Yannick Buchholz, Dara Hallinan, and Jonas Kuitert. 2023. 'E2.2.1: Bericht Vertragsrechtliche Überprüfung Und Compliance'. FAIR Data Spaces Project Deliverable E2.2.1.
- Christoforaki, Maria. 2021. 'ELSA Training for Data Scientists-Describing the Landscape'. FAIR-DS Project Deliverable E 4.5.1. Cologne: UzK. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7233569>.
- . 2022. 'Data Scientists and ELSA: Describing the Landscape'. June 1. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6637759>.
- . 2023. 'ELSA Training Curriculum for Data Scientists - Version 1.0'. FAIR-DS Project Deliverable E 4.5.3. Cologne: UzK. <https://zenodo.org/record/8318726>.
- Christoforaki, Maria, and Oya Beyan. 2022. 'AI Ethics—A Bird's Eye View'. *AI Ethics—A Bird's Eye View* 12 (9): 4130. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12094130>.
- Christoforaki, Maria, and Oya Deniz Beyan. 2024. 'Towards an ELSA Curriculum for Data Scientists'. *AI* 5 (2): 504–15. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ai5020025>.
- Cleveland, William S. 2001. 'Data Science: An Action Plan for Expanding the Technical Areas of the Field of Statistics'. *International Statistical Review* 69 (1): 21–26.

-
- Crawford, Kate. 2021. *Atlas of AI: Power, Politics, and the Planetary Costs of Artificial Intelligence*. New Haven: Yale University Press.
- Emmert-Streib, Frank, and Matthias Dehmer. 2019. 'Defining Data Science by a Data-Driven Quantification of the Community'. *Machine Learning and Knowledge Extraction* 1 (1): 235–51. <https://doi.org/10.3390/make1010015>.
- Engelhardt, Claudia. 2022. *How to Be FAIR with Your Data: A Teaching and Training Handbook for Higher Education Institutions*. Göttingen: Göttingen University Press. <https://doi.org/10.17875/gup2022-1915>.
- 'Ethical Guidelines - Gesellschaft Für Informatik e.V.' 2018. 29 June 2018. <https://gi.de/ethicalguidelines>.
- European Commission, Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology. 2021. *Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL LAYING DOWN HARMONISED RULES ON ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ACT) AND AMENDING CERTAIN UNION LEGISLATIVE ACTS*. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52021PC0206>.
- European Parliament, Council of the European Union. 2016. *Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the Protection of Natural Persons with Regard to the Processing of Personal Data and on the Free Movement of Such Data, and Repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) (Text with EEA Relevance)*. OJ L. Vol. 119. <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj/eng>.
- Floridi, Luciano. 2019. 'Translating Principles into Practices of Digital Ethics: Five Risks of Being Unethical'. *Philosophy & Technology* 32 (2): 185–93. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13347-019-00354-x>.
- Floridi, Luciano, Josh Cowls, Monica Beltrametti, Raja Chatila, Patrice Chazerand, Virginia Dignum, Christoph Luetge, et al. 2018. 'AI4People—An Ethical Framework for a Good AI Society: Opportunities, Risks, Principles, and Recommendations'. *Minds and Machines* 28 (4): 689–707. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11023-018-9482-5>.
- French, Robert M. 1999. 'Catastrophic Forgetting in Connectionist Networks'. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences* 3 (4): 128–35. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1364-6613\(99\)01294-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1364-6613(99)01294-2).
- High-Level Expert Group on AI (AI HLEG). 2019. 'Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI'. Brussels: European Commission. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>.
- Jaberansary, Mehrshad, Macedo Maia, Yeliz Ucer Yediel, Oya Beyan, and Toralf Kirsten. 2023. 'Analyzing Distributed Medical Data in FAIR Data Spaces'. In *WWW '23 Companion*. Austin, TX, USA.
- Leslie, David. 2019. 'Understanding Artificial Intelligence Ethics and Safety: A Guide for the Responsible Design and Implementation of AI Systems in the Public Sector'. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.3240529>.
- McNamara, Andrew, Justin Smith, and Emerson Murphy-Hill. 2018. 'Does ACM's Code of Ethics Change Ethical Decision Making in Software Development?' In *Proceedings of the 2018 26th ACM Joint Meeting on European Software Engineering Conference and Symposium on the Foundations of Software Engineering*, 729–33. Lake Buena Vista FL USA: ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3236024.3264833>.
- Mittelstadt, Brent. 2019. 'Principles Alone Cannot Guarantee Ethical AI'. *Nature Machine Intelligence* 1 (11): 501–7. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42256-019-0114-4>.
- Morley, Jessica, Luciano Floridi, Libby Kinsey, and Anat Elhalal. 2020. 'From What to How: An

-
- Initial Review of Publicly Available AI Ethics Tools, Methods and Research to Translate Principles into Practices'. *Science and Engineering Ethics* 26 (4): 2141–68. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-019-00165-5>.
- Reich, Rob, Mehran Sahami, Jeremy M. Weinstein, and Hilary Cohen. 2020. 'Teaching Computer Ethics: A Deeply Multidisciplinary Approach'. In *Proceedings of the 51st ACM Technical Symposium on Computer Science Education*, 296–302. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3328778.3366951>.
- Saltz, Jeffrey S., and Neil Dewar. 2019. 'Data Science Ethical Considerations: A Systematic Literature Review and Proposed Project Framework'. *Ethics and Information Technology* 21 (3): 197–208. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10676-019-09502-5>.
- Shearer, Colin. 2000. 'The CRISP-DM Model: The New Blueprint for Data Mining'. *Journal of Data Warehousing* 5 (4): 13–22.
- Unabhängiges Landeszentrum für Datenschutz, ed. 2020a. 'Das Standard-Datenschutzmodell (SDM) - ULD'. AK Technik der Konferenz der unabhängigen Datenschutzaufsichtsbehörden des Bundes und der Länder. <https://www.datenschutzzentrum.de/sdm/>.
- , ed. 2020b. 'The Standard Data Protection Model'. AK Technik of the Independent Data Protection Supervisory Authorities of the Federation and the Länder. https://www.datenschutzzentrum.de/uploads/sdm/SDM-Methodology_V2.0b.pdf.
- Via, Allegra, Patricia M. Palagi, Jessica M. Lindvall, Rochelle E. Tractenberg, and Teresa K. Attwood. 2020. 'Course Design: Considerations for Trainers—a Professional Guide'. *F1000Research* 9 (1377): 1377.
- Welten, Sascha, Yongli Mou, Laurenz Neumann, Mehrshad Jaberansary, Yeliz Yediel Ucer, Toralf Kirsten, Stefan Decker, and Oya Beyan. 2022. 'A Privacy-Preserving Distributed Analytics Platform for Health Care Data'. *Methods of Information in Medicine* 61 (S 01): e1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0041-1740564>.
- 'WP3 WP4 Technical Foundations and Demonstrators'. n.d. GitHub. Accessed 14 March 2023. <https://github.com/FAIR-DS4NFDI/FAIR-DSWiki/wiki/WP3-WP4-Technical-Foundations-and-Demonstrators>.

Appendices

Appendix I: KUs Table

Business Understanding	Data Understanding	Data Preparation	Modelling	Evaluation	Deployment
KU I.1: Stakeholder identification	KU II.1: Data Protection	KU III.1: Data Protection	KU IV.1: Model bias and mitigation techniques	KU V.1: Evaluation beyond accuracy	KU VI.1: System deployment limitations
KU I.2: Incorporating community values	KU II.2: Data bias during collection and challenges in ways to mitigate it	KU III.2: Data challenges in preprocessing	KU IV.2: Model transparency and explicability	KU V.2: Fairness	KU VI.2: Visualisation bias
KU I.3: Organisational culture	KU II.3: Intellectual property issues and licences	KU III.3: Intellectual property issues of training data	KU IV.3: Environmental impact of model training	KU V.5: Model documentation	KU VI.3: Accountability and processes to ensure it
KU I.4: Basic Legal concepts	KU II.4: Ethics dumping in data collection	KU III.4: Ethics dumping in data preprocessing	KU IV.4: Intellectual property issues		
	KU II.5: Dataset documentation	KU III.5: Dataset documentation	KU IV.5: Model documentation		

Appendix II-Survey results

A. Horizon Europe Shift-Hub Project Open Innovation Workshop Survey Results

The following are the survey results from the workshop. The questions could have multiple answers.

slido

slido

slido

slido

slido

B. ELSA Training Survey in English

ELSA Training Survey queries

Introduction

The following Survey is developed in the framework of the [FAIR Data Spaces](#) project (a collaboration between Gaia-X and NFDI) and is a kind request for feedback from the Gaia-X members regarding ELSA (ethical, legal, and social aspects) training for data scientists. It consists of 5 check-box ticking questions.

More details on the Framework

The [FAIR Data Spaces](#) project is funded by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) and aims to connect the Gaia-X federated and secure data infrastructure and the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) to a common, cloud-based data space for industry and research in compliance with the FAIR Principles, i.e., to share data in a findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable way.

Part of the project is also to develop a set of core elements for ELSA (ethical, legal, and social aspects) training for data scientists, which led to the publication of a first version of an [ELSA Curriculum](#).

Survey

1. Which subjects should primarily be taught (more than one answer possible)

Stakeholder identification and impact assessment	<input type="checkbox"/>
Professional codes of values/conduct	<input type="checkbox"/>
Basic legal concepts	<input type="checkbox"/>
Bias and mitigation	<input type="checkbox"/>
Data protection	<input type="checkbox"/>
Intellectual Property	<input type="checkbox"/>
Transparency and explicability	<input type="checkbox"/>
Evaluation beyond accuracy	<input type="checkbox"/>

Environmental impact of model training	<input type="checkbox"/>
Auditing	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other (please specify)	

2. What kind of format the training could be:

Intensive training (1-2 months)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Summer/Winter School (1-2 weeks)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Workshop series on specific topics (2-3 days per topic)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Workshops on special topics (4 half days per topic)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other (please specify)	

3. Which level of knowledge should the training offer:

Introductory in a variety of topics	<input type="checkbox"/>
Deep dives into specific topics (legal, technical, etc)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Both depending on the audience	<input type="checkbox"/>
Both depending on the format and duration	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other (please specify)	

4. What type of audience is appropriate for this training:

Data scientists at the beginning of their career	<input type="checkbox"/>
Experienced data scientists	<input type="checkbox"/>
Managers and Technical Directors	<input type="checkbox"/>
All the above depending on the format and duration	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other (please specify)	

5. Who should provide such a course:

Academic Institutions as part of their studies	<input type="checkbox"/>
Academic Institutions as independent programs addressed to all that are interested	<input type="checkbox"/>
Specialized training centres	<input type="checkbox"/>
Companies (e.g. via HR)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other (please specify)	

Results

Domain of expertise

20 responses

Do you currently/have you in the past worked for a data science project?

22 responses

Do you have any knowledge/experience about ELSA issues in data science

22 responses

1. Which subjects should primarily be taught

22 responses

2. What kind of format the training could be:

22 responses

3. Which level of knowledge should the training offer:

22 responses

4. What type of audience is appropriate for this training:

22 responses

5. Who should provide such a course:

22 responses

C. ELSA Training Survey in German

ELSA-Ausbildungsumfrage-Fragen

Einleitung

Die folgende Umfrage wurde im Rahmen des FAIR Data Spaces-Projekts (eine Zusammenarbeit zwischen Gaia-X und NFDI) entwickelt und ist eine freundliche Bitte an die Gaia-X-Mitglieder um Feedback zu ELSA (ethische, rechtliche und soziale Aspekte) - Schulungen für Datenwissenschaftler. Es besteht aus 5 Fragen zum Ankreuzen

Mehr Details zum Framework

Das Projekt FAIR Data Spaces wird vom Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung (BMBF) gefördert und zielt darauf ab, die föderierte und sichere Dateninfrastruktur von Gaia-X und die Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI) zu einem gemeinsamen, cloudbasierten Datenraum für Industrie und Forschung zu verbinden, der den FAIR-Prinzipien entspricht, d.h. Daten auffindbar, zugänglich, interoperabel und wiederverwendbar zu machen.

Teil des Projekts ist auch die Entwicklung einer Reihe von Kernelementen für ELSA-Schulungen (ethische, rechtliche und soziale Aspekte) für Datenwissenschaftler, was zur Veröffentlichung einer ersten Version eines ELSA-Lehrplans führte.

Fragen

1. Welche Fächer sollten vorrangig unterrichtet werden (mehrere Antworten möglich)

Identifizierung von Stakeholdern und Folgenabschätzung	<input type="checkbox"/>
Berufliche Werte/Verhaltenskodexe	<input type="checkbox"/>
Rechtliche Grundbegriffe	<input type="checkbox"/>

Vorurteile und Schadensbegrenzung	<input type="checkbox"/>
Datenschutz	<input type="checkbox"/>
Geistiges Eigentum	<input type="checkbox"/>
Transparenz und Erklärbarkeit	<input type="checkbox"/>
Bewertung über die Genauigkeit hinaus	<input type="checkbox"/>
Umweltauswirkungen der Modellschulung	<input type="checkbox"/>
Rechnungsprüfung	<input type="checkbox"/>
Sonstiges (bitte angeben)	

2. Welches Format die Schulung haben könnte:

Intensive Ausbildung (1-2 Monate)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Sommer-/Winterschule (1-2 Wochen)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Workshop-Reihe zu spezifischen Themen (2-3 Tage pro Thema)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Workshops zu speziellen Themen (4 halbe Tage pro Thema)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Sonstiges (bitte angeben)	

3. Welchen Wissensstand sollte die Ausbildung bieten?

Einführung in eine Vielzahl von Themen	<input type="checkbox"/>
Vertiefung bestimmter Themen (rechtlich, technisch usw.)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Beides hängt vom Publikum ab	<input type="checkbox"/>
Beides je nach Format und Dauer	<input type="checkbox"/>
Sonstiges (bitte angeben)	

4. Welche Art von Publikum ist für diese Schulung geeignet?

Datenwissenschaftler am Anfang ihrer Karriere	<input type="checkbox"/>
Erfahrene Datenwissenschaftler	<input type="checkbox"/>
Manager und technische Direktoren	<input type="checkbox"/>

Alle oben genannten Punkte je nach Format und Dauer	<input type="checkbox"/>
Sonstiges (bitte angeben)	

5. Wer sollte einen solchen Kurs anbieten?

Akademische Einrichtungen als Teil ihres Studiums	<input type="checkbox"/>
Akademische Einrichtungen als unabhängige Programme, die sich an alle Interessierten richten	<input type="checkbox"/>
Spezialisierte Ausbildungszentren	<input type="checkbox"/>
Unternehmen (z. B. über HR)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Sonstiges (bitte angeben)	

Results

1. Welche Themen sollten vorrangig unterrichtet werden

4 responses

2. Welches Format sollte die Schulung haben:

4 responses

3. Welchen Wissensstand sollte die Schulung bieten?

4 responses

An welche Zielgruppe soll sich die Schulung richten?

4 responses

D. Combined results of the survey in English and German

1. Which subjects should primarily be taught

2. What kind of format the training could be

3. Which level of knowledge should the training offer:

4. What type of audience is appropriate for this training

5. Who should provide such a course

E. Combined results of all surveys

E1. Graphs of results

1. Which subjects should primally be taught

2. What kind of format the training could be

3. Which level of knowledge should the training offer

4. What type of audience is appropriate for this training

5. Who should provide such a course

E2.Comparative table for each survey and combined results

	Internet survey	Shift-Hub	Total
Subjects taught	Data protection Basic legal concepts Transparency and explicability Bias and mitigation Intellectual Property Professional codes of values/conduct Environmental impact of model training Stakeholder identification and impact assessment Evaluation beyond accuracy Auditing	Stakeholder identification and impact assessment Basic legal concepts Intellectual Property Evaluation beyond accuracy Transparency and explicability Environmental impact of model training Data protection Professional codes of values/conduct Bias and mitigation Auditing	Basic legal concepts Data protection Stakeholder identification and impact assessment Transparency and explicability Intellectual Property Bias and mitigation Evaluation beyond accuracy Environmental impact of model training Professional codes of values/conduct Auditing
Format of training	Summer/Winter School (1-2 weeks) Workshops on special topics (4 half days per topic) Workshop series on specific topics (2-3 days per topic) Intensive training (1-2 months)	Workshop series on specific topics (2-3 days per topic) Summer/Winter School (1-2 weeks) Workshops on special topics (4 half days per topic) Intensive training (1-2 months)	Workshop series on specific topics (2-3 days per topic) Summer/Winter School (1-2 weeks) Workshops on special topics (4 half days per topic) Intensive training (1-2 months)
Level of knowledge	Both depending on the audience Both depending on the format and duration Deep dives to specific topics (legal, technical, etc) Introductory in a variety of topics	Both depending on the audience Deep dives to specific topics (legal, technical, etc) Both depending on the format and duration Introductory in a variety of topics	Both depending on the audience Both depending on the format and duration Deep dives to specific topics (legal, technical, etc) Introductory in a variety of topics
Type of audience	All the above depending on the format and duration Data scientists at the beginning of their career Managers and Technical Directors Experienced data scientists	All the above depending on the format and duration Data scientists at the beginning of their career Experienced data scientists Managers and Technical Directors	All the above depending on the format and duration Data scientists at the beginning of their career Managers and Technical Directors Experienced data scientists
Provider type	Academic Institutions as independent programs addressed to all that are interested Academic Institutions as part of their studies Specialized training centres Companies (e.g. via HR)	Specialized training centres Academic Institutions as independent programs addressed to all that are interested Academic Institutions as part of their studies Companies (e.g. via HR)	Academic Institutions as independent programs addressed to all that are interested Specialized training centres Academic Institutions as part of their studies Companies (e.g. via HR)

<https://www.nfdi.de/fair-data-spaces/>

#FAIRDataSpaces @FAIRDataSpaces

<https://www.nfdi.de/fair-data-spaces-newsletter/>